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MEDICAL CENTERS AND THE RUSSIAN ORTHODOX CHURCH: DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS

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Abstract:

In article examines the participation and assistance of the Orthodox Church in solving problems that allowed to give a scientific justification for the cooperation of health care and Orthodox religious institutions, to determine their role in the historical context and structure of modern healthcare in Russia. The article presents an algorithm for organizing sisters of mercy, their system of upbringing. Particular attention is given to the possibility of teaching the course "Foundations of Orthodox Culture" in secular educational institutions.

Research materials can serve as a basis for the formation of morally sound positions of medical workers and the population on the main problems of medical activity.

Based on the study, the authors published a series of articles in which the experience of the work of the Orthodox Church in the charitable sphere has been summarized. This experience can be used to create new charitable institutions, including those who provided medical assistance.

In preparing the article, the authors used concrete historical, civilizational, formational and social methods of research that allowed us to uncover facts, phenomena and processes in the interconnection and unity of the past, present and future.

Keywords: Medicine, church, charity, state, priest.

I. INTRODUCTION

State-church relations as a combination of historically emerging and changing forms of relations between state institutions and religious organizations are one of the main parts of the domestic and foreign policies of any state. Russia has always been a multi-confessional country, here all major religious confessions coexist: Christianity, Buddhism, Islam, Judaism. At the same time, in the modern Russian consciousness there is a close connection between Orthodoxy and national identity. 80-82% of the population of Russia consider themselves Orthodox. The role of the Russian Orthodox Church in the economic and social life of the country was significant throughout the history of the country until October 1917. Even in the Old Russian period, the spiritual foundations of charity were formed under the influence of

self-consciousness. Since the late 1980's. in our country, the gradual return of the Church to the sphere of charity and medical and social services began, the process of uniting the interests of the Church and the state in the field of protecting human health was intensified.

The main legal documents in this area were the "Fundamentals of Legislation on the Protection of Health of Citizens in the Russian Federation" of 1993 and the "Agreement on Cooperation between the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation and the Russian Orthodox Church." The importance of the church mission in the health sector was expressed in the creation of hospital temples, church hospitals and an almshouse. The number of monasteries engaged in social activities is increasing, fraternities are being organized. At the same time, the catastrophic situation in the field of public health in Russia is growing. The state public health system is developing mainly around the world, the volume of medical care often increases without regard for quality.

Many researchers believe that the public health system can not function effectively under the current conditions. In this connection, studies that reflect the relationship between the Church and medical institutions in modern Russia are of great importance.

II. METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in the methodological field of the sociology of medicine. The research program was of a multistage nature and provided for the use of a methodology based on traditional methods of socio-hygienic, medical-organizational and historical-analytical nature, adapted to the specifics of the purposes followed by statistical processing and data analysis. In the work to achieve the goal and implement research tasks, a number of methods of concrete sociology are offered: a survey, in-depth interviews, expert interviews, content analysis, a biographical method.

The organizational chart of the interaction of Orthodox organizations and bodies of practical health, developed in this article, is based on historical traditions of the charitable activities of the Russian Orthodox Church. This scheme takes into account modern socio-economic realities. This scheme proved to be effective in the organization of medical care and can serve as a basic model for the development of cooperation between the Church and medical institutions. Given the deep historical evidence of the important role of Orthodox Christianity in preserving health and creating a healthy lifestyle for the population, it should be recognized that the development of special programs for cooperation between medical organizations and the Church is justified in modern conditions.

III. RESULTS

The article shows the results, which testify that medical and social assistance to the population of Russia is mainly under the aegis of monasteries. The nature and scope of this assistance in different periods were not the same and depended on the policy of state power towards the Church. If at the initial stages of the country's development there were no other shelters for the sick and disabled, with the exception of monasteries. By the beginning of the 20th century, shelters occupied a leading position in state, public and charitable organizations. They created a unique system of medical and social assistance to the population. The church has been active in this area since the late 1980s, and both traditional and new forms and methods of medico-social and charitable work were realized.

The cooperation of the Church and the state in the field of health and social services, the legal basis of which is in the process of formation, testifies to the recognition of the Church in the life of Russian society, contributes to the expansion of social health and the participation of a wide range of people to solve health problems and revive the spiritual traditions of medicine. The Orthodox Church provides medical and social assistance to the following groups of people: terminal, somatic, mental, HIV-infected, drug addicts, patients

with toxic and alcoholic diseases. The expediency of creating hospitals for religious confessions as a whole was recognized by 41.7% of doctors and 46.1% of patients.

In addition, it can be noted that the main types of institutions that are actively engaged in medical and social activities are: a) medical institutions of a stationary type, incl. hospitals operating under the Moscow Patriarchate, diocesan hospitals, monastery hospitals, hospitals in theological schools; (b) outpatient medical facilities, including first aid centers for religious schools, monastic medical posts; (c) Medical and social institutions. For example, the diocesan hospital of Saint Blessed Xenia helps orphans and elderly people. The average length of stay in the hospital is 31 days. Among the patients, pensioners were 95.4%, disabled people - 71.3%, lonely - 30.4%. The hospital staff was selected from among Orthodox believers. The satisfaction of patients with treatment is high (98.4%) and the ratio of medical personnel (100.0%).

A special form of medical and social activities of the Church are care centers (in 2016 in the Russian Federation, 14), designed for outpatient rehabilitation of mentally ill, alcoholics and drug addicts affected by totalitarian sects, psychics. The task of Orthodox priests and doctors is to closely cooperate in these centers. The course of rehabilitation takes an average of 1-2 years.

In addition to institutions, the Church creates medical organizations that carry out their ministry in public medical and social institutions: for example, the society of Orthodox doctors; sisterhood of mercy, brotherhood of mercy, parish communities of hospital temples. The Society of Orthodox Physicians is a new form of association of medical workers for Russia on the basis of a religious community. Their goal is to provide medical and spiritual assistance to sick poor people, coordinate the activities of charitable brotherhoods and sisterhoods, organize a system of qualified diagnostic, therapeutic and preventive care for churchmen, discuss current medical problems in accordance with the canons of the Orthodox Church. For example, the society in Moscow consists of medical, scientific and educational and training departments. For the years 2000-2016. The number of people seeking help was about 25,000 people. Training courses for Orthodox doctors and psychologists have been organized.

Today, the centers of the sisters of mercy, organized in Russia in the XIX century, demonstrated their effectiveness. Based on the analysis of the development of nursing, five main stages (periods) of the movement of nurses in Russia were identified. The distinctive features of this movement were medical and social assistance, strict morality, love and charity toward one's neighbor, diligence and dedication, discipline. In 2016, there are about 40 communities and groups of sisters of mercy in Russia. An algorithm for creating a community of sisters of mercy is developed and conceptual principles of its organization are formulated.

The main thing is to find a job for a sister, where she can perform church obedience in addition to medical, within the framework of jointly developed contract documents regulating the status and order of service in the conditions of a particular institution. Clearly organized sisterhoods, consisting of religious, morally educated and at the same time professionally trained sisters, can undoubtedly provide more effective assistance to public health institutions and social workers, since there is a shortage of medical specialists of junior and middle level.

The activities of nurses, based on Christian charity, combine medical care with spiritual care for the patient. The main goal of the sisterhood was to strengthen the moral and spiritual foundations of society.

As a result, today the revival of the brotherly and sister movement is an objective process of returning to traditional forms of religious life in Russia. At the same time, the current socio-economic situation in the country does not allow many Orthodox movements and organizations to revive the church and social life and fully understand the tasks of social services.

Despite the positive results in the social and philanthropic activities of individual brotherhoods and sisterhoods, the author believes that the revival of the sister movement is associated with the same problems that led to the suspension of the work of Orthodox brotherhoods. Today, 150 brotherhoods and sisterhoods registered with the Ministry of Justice of the Russian Federation operate independently and in isolation, without information and coordination

However, despite the artificial suppression of the fraternal movement, the Unions of Orthodox brotherhoods should be attributed to institutions that seek to mobilize community and church organizations to jointly solve social, spiritual and ethical problems. In these unions, new technologies are being developed in various fields of medicine.

In the percentage ratio, it looks like this.

Thus, history shows that such forms of Orthodox life as brotherhood and sisterhood, unlike secular and some church institutions, can not be created or canceled only "from above". They are based on believers and want to fulfill one or another church ministry together.

IV. DISCUSSION

Some aspects of the participation of the Russian Orthodox Church in protecting public health were examined in the works of Mirsky MB, Pospelovsky D., Siluyanova IV, Filimonova SV, Cherkasova AE. and other domestic scientists. However, few works are devoted to a comprehensive study of the interaction of the Russian Orthodox Church with medical personnel. Almost in the scientific literature, there was no analysis of the participation of the Russian Orthodox Church in protecting the health of the population of the Voronezh Region.

The author of this article proposes to classify various aspects of the historiography of this problem by periods. The first historiographical period - from the beginning of the XIX century to the 70-ies. At that time, a complex historical work was carried out to collect and publish materials that had the character of historical data, reference data, the Charter of various institutions of public charity and education. Studies were often one-sided and subjective, devoid of profound scientific medical analysis.

The second historiographical period from the 70s. XIX century until 1917. During this period, a great leap was made in historical science for the collection, processing and publication of official documents and extensive factual materials, as well as bibliographic indexes. In the works of EE Golubinsky, AP Dobrolonsky, SG Runkevich, Runovsky, Znamensky, Klyuchevsky, Barsov, FV Blagovidov, B. Titlipov, B.II. Kudryavtseva, Papkova, Prugavina, Makariya (Bulgakova), Berdyaeva, various aspects of the development of medical charity were systematized. Scientists also considered the medical and social role of church parishes in the development of assistance to the needy.

There was a significant amount of biographical work, about the most vivid representatives of the parish clergy and their ministry. Statistical information on the total number of medical societies and fraternities in the Russian Empire is also found in the encyclopedia "Russia", published in 1898. A valuable group are modern published reports and surveys that contain data on the history of the church and statistical work.

Therefore, the relevance of studying the problems associated with the embodiment of Christian ideals in medical practice, both public and secular authors, is topical.

Thus, in this article, all of the above indicates the necessity and importance of scientific research, conducted in terms of a systematic approach, in-depth analysis, justification and implementation of results in educational and medical institutions.

V. CONCLUSION

Currently, the medical and social charitable activities of the Russian Orthodox Church are actively developing. The cooperation of Orthodox organizations with medical institutions can give such positive results as: the revival of the spiritual traditions of medicine; awareness of the interdependence of man's spiritual and physical health; attraction of additional financial, organizational and especially human resources for medical care; formation of morally grounded positions of medical workers and the population on the main problems of medical ethics (bioethics); formation of a healthy lifestyle of the population and combating the spread of bad habits; expansion of the base of social health and involvement of the general public in solving health problems.

The views of doctors and patients on the problems of clinical ethics (the relationship between a doctor and a patient, including the ethics of informing, obtaining informed consent for treatment, confidence indicators, medical secrets, etc.) are not very dependent on their attitude to the Orthodox faith. In the performance of their duties, most doctors prefer professional views on medicine.

The opinions of many doctors and patients about modern medical technologies are not yet formed, they have no solid moral justification. There are significant differences in the assessment of modern biotechnology of doctors and patients, depending on their religious affiliations, and the views of church members are more in line with the norms of religious morality and medical ethics. The organizational chart of the interaction of Orthodox organizations and bodies of practical health, developed in this article, is based on historical traditions of the charitable activities of the Russian Orthodox Church. This scheme takes into account modern socio-economic realities, has proved effective in the organization of medical services and can become a basic model for the development of cooperation between the Church and medical institutions.

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PHOTOGRAPHIC APPLICATIONS

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DERIVATIONAL POTENTIAL OF THE LATIN VOCABULARY THROUGH SPACE AND TIME: WHERE SYSTEM MEETS CREATIVITY

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Abstract:

The creation of real texts in Latin can be regarded not only as the intellectual activity of the pastime of a limited number of enthusiasts, but also a long linguistic experiment. In this study, the product of such linguistic activity serves as a source of materials, primarily lexical and derivational innovations, for analyzing events that may arise in a "restored" language system. To reveal trends in the development of linguistic material and its potential, the data obtained from new Latin texts were compared with the results of studying Latin borrowings in English (in the natural conditions of a living language). Obviously, the choice of vocabulary and new terms to denote modern realities in these new Latin news texts are subject to the preferences of individual researchers and are sometimes arbitrary to a greater extent than in the case of creating text in a naturally developing language, where the speaker / user strongly dominates the usage norms. In addition, when developing innovations, the authors of the texts in question inevitably follow their native language of the L2 experience. As a result of innovation, the "New Latin Scheme" shows some features more typical of modern European languages, in addition, the main development trends in the group of Latin borrowings in English were different from those found in the lexicon of the new Latin.

Keywords: Latin, Latin borrowings, word formation, derivation, language system, English, semantic development, chasing, dictionary.

I. INTRODUCTION

Preserving interest in classical languages in the academic environment of some European and non-European countries, in particular, the production of new texts with the means of language systems that have long been abandoned in 'natural' communication is a vivid example of the policy encouraging multiculturalism and the multilingualism in modern society.

Newly produced texts in Latin (hereinafter referred to as "new Latin") are the creations of a limited circle of persons, connoisseurs and enthusiasts of classical philology, whose linguistic creativity range is very wide and varied both in terms of genre and in themes. However, it is the most intriguing fact that there is a certain sphere that allows the Latin language to function outside instructional and academic applications, as a means of communicating the most relevant information. This primarily includes news texts that cover current and urgent events (both national and global) and are published on the Internet sites of several European mass media. The number of authors of such texts is very limited, and the authorship is mandatory.

One of the most curious phenomena in this regard is coining innovations to denote modern realities using the repertory of the classical language. While being a remarkable example of the actualization of the linguistic system potential, such creativity within system and means of the extinct languages raises a number of questions in the aspect of theoretical linguistics. And if the very phenomenon of generating new linguistic units semasiologically and morphologically only confirms postulates concerning the possibilities of developing a linguistic system in conditions of a communicative need, i.e. when the language performs its primary functions, the question of the "legitimacy" of these newly coined units, their adaptation in the system, and their fixation as stable elements of the inventory of linguistic units makes us recall the artificial conditions of such a linguistic experiment. Thus, the question of the relationship between the natural and the artificial in this language creativity act becomes the key issue. One of the aspects in considering it is the interaction of the individual and systemic vectors, that is free creativity (of an individual author) and constraints in the process of generating new vocabulary units.

The impulse of linguistic creativity in the prevailing extralinguistic conditions is inevitably guided by the reflection of the author-creator (or group of authors). Alongside with the obvious considerations of communicative (the expected result is the message delivered to the addressee) and the semantic (the result is the most precise term and meaning) dimensions, the considerable importance in this case is attached to such subjectively significant characteristics as "prestige" and euphony of the expression.

One can treat such a phenomenon as "new Latin" differently, regarding it as the activity of a group of enthusiasts who construct texts with actual content utilizing the material of an ancient language. Whether it is a curiosity, an intellectual hobby, a language simulation game, or just a game for fun, in this study we approach this unique material as an interesting phenomenon and peculiar linguistic experiment that reveals the potential of the language and allows us to compare the development of a language under natural (as it were) conditions and a language that is "revived" as a result of artificial reconstruction and simulation of speech activity with the means of "mothballed" material of the Latin language. For the linguist, it opens up the possibility of interesting theoretical generalizations, testing hypotheses about the specific features of the development of various language subsystems.

The topic of Latin heritage in English cannot be avoided in any comprehensive study on the history of English, a number of researches in historical lexicology being devoted specifically to Latin loanwords. Given the considerable number of papers on the peculiarities of penetration, adaptation and further development of the borrowed Latin vocabulary in English, observations on this issue will only be summarized further with regard to Modern English.

If the earliest borrowings from Latin into English occurred as a result of direct contacts between the speakers of the two languages, then starting from around the early 14th century, Latin words began to enter English in a completely different way – through the translation of texts (primarily religious ones). It is well known when the translator was not able to find an adequate unit in the English lexicon, he transferred a Latin word in the "anglicized" form the translated text into the target language. Later, in the 15th and 16th centuries it became a common practice among many translators of academic works, as well as authors of new texts already in English.

It is on the period of the New Time and the Renaissance of the 15th – 17th centuries that the peak of borrowing fell, when the English vocabulary was enriched with immense number of borrowings in the sphere of science and humanities. The authors of this time could not help but feel the influence of the centuries-old tradition of medieval Latin as the language of science. A very important feature of this broad, however, indirect and "bookish", stream of contacts of the two languages was the borrowing of word-formation elements. Word-formation models as such are known to be borrowed very rarely, but such a massive intervention in English vocabulary, both directly from Latin and from French, led to the fact that the affixes in borrowings were perceived as a separate morpheme and clearly distinguished already in a new language the material. Words were often borrowed not in isolation, but in the form of word-building nests, "due to this, a certain formal order was created" for the newly borrowed words in the borrowing language. Thus, easily identifiable derivational affixes gave new formations now with English stems, the so-called hybrids: readable, talk-ative, false-hood, use-less, merci-ful (Latin root - Germanic suffix); mis-creant (German prefix with

Latin root). It was during the Middle and Early English periods in English that most of the models that are productive now were widely distributed and actively developed (see more detailed in Logunov).

II. METHODOLOGY

This paper considers the derivational development of Latin vocabulary items in the course of functioning of linguistic material both in the “new Latin” discourse and after their borrowing in the new European languages. The Latin lexical innovations proper and the peculiarities of further semantic derivational development and word formation in the vocabulary items borrowed from Latin are compared and discussed. These processes will be analyzed in terms of the complex interaction of the systemic language development and individual language creativity. To identify the developments taking place in the examined category of lexis we have to resort to the dictionaries reflecting various historical stages of material and semantic “life” of Latin roots, affixes and complete lexemes. The first reference is made to the forms and meanings as they are recorded in the dictionaries of classical Latin (occasionally involving material from the late Latin period), mostly, Oxford Latin Dictionary Online (OLDo) and Dvoretzky.

In order to correlate the material of the source languages as it existed before exiting a new language (English, in the case) with already borrowed words/roots as they now function in the borrower language, the comparison of semantics and forms of classical Latin vocabulary units with borrowed English ones was performed based on the data of English dictionaries providing necessary information of historical aspect (first appearance/recording date, contexts, obsolete meanings, etc.): Shorter Oxford English Dictionary (SOED) and Webster’s Third New International Dictionary of English (Webster’s). This procedure allowed us to trace the mainstream trends of assimilation and development of abundant Latin heritage in Modern English, with the emphasis laid on the ways of derivation (both in terms of word form and semantic development). At the same time, the data of classical Latin dictionaries were used to find the cases of semantic variations in the New Latin lexicon.

The results may serve as a reference for considering developments occurring within the scope of New Latin material. The vocabulary for analyses was obtained by continuous sampling from the texts of aforementioned web resources. In the cases where the meaning of a word or phrase in such newly created texts was hard to define contextual analyses with reference to extralinguistic realia was applied. Thus, the innovations identified in the New Latin lexicon could be compared with the products of development of the Latin borrowed elements in English under natural conditions.

III. RESULTS

This paper does not cover the words which entered English as a result of direct contact between the speakers of the Old German dialects and the Late Latin, and the words borrowed through the mediation of French. The focus of our interest is, primarily, the results of “book bilingualism” leading to the conscious and reflected, to some extent, processes of interaction between new and classical languages. The cases of such realized conscious borrowings, filling lacunae of the language (including stylistically, with the replacement of lexical units from the layers of everyday vocabulary with the words of a “prestigious” classical language) are of special significance as they represent a process of systematic knowledge categorization. The lexical subsystem of language responds most flexibly to the needs of speakers for the expression of developing concepts, this process involving the word-formation potential of the system.

The bookish nature of borrowing often leads to the borrowing of the word not in a single isolated meaning, but to the “systemic” borrowing of both the basic and figurative meanings of words. For example, the noun *auditio*, when borrowed into English, retains the meaning of the act or process of ‘hearing’ and the importance of possessing ‘sense of hearing’. Obviously, borrowings acquire new combinatory characteristics when they are used to describe new relevant concepts and phenomena, for example, the

adjective *equable* (from *Latinaequabilis*, *e*) in English is collocated with the noun *temperature*, characterizing this parameter with a property of constancy.

It might be presumed that in adapting to the English vocabulary Latin borrowings would have retained specific meanings, since these lexemes were borrowed for using within specific conceptual fields of communication, whereas the most basic, primary meanings would not have been transferred into the new language. However, this is not always the case. It was not uncommon for a borrowed unit to preserve and develop precisely the primary meaning that was relevant for the general core of the vocabulary, terminological meanings due to the change of denotation becoming irrelevant (for example, due to differences in the norms of the Roman and the new national law, as well as in connection with the change in the scientific picture of the world). For instance, the Latin nouns *aequatio* and *exclusio* had special meanings in the legal sphere: “uniform distribution (as of property, income)” and “refusal to accept a claim” respectively. Sometimes only a concrete, material meaning was borrowed, while the abstract ones existing in Latin turned out to be irrelevant for the new language: cf. *corpulent* - 'burly, fat, fat, fat' from the Lat. *corpulentus* – “1) corpulent, fat, full; 4) corporeal, physical” or *procreate* - 'spawn' from the Lat. *procreo* – “1) to bring into existence: 2) to produce, create”.

Numerous borrowings are fully assimilated by the English language, which proves their considerable potential in the development of semantics. The new meanings of the borrowed Latinisms developed both metonymically (English armaments from the Latin *armamentum* received, in addition to the former meaning of 'weapons, arming' the new meaning 'armed forces'), and metaphorically (for example, the adjective *arbitrary* based on the meaning 'whimsical' developed the meaning 'capricious' and 'despotic').

As was noted above, the massive introduction of Latin vocabulary into English resulted in enriching the latter with world-formation nests; however the composition of these nests is often heterogeneous in the direct source of lexical units and in the time of their borrowing. This fact also prompts some interesting assumptions.

Such a systematization of newly borrowed and previously adopted elements leads to cases of “reverse” word formation, when the composition of a previously borrowed (from French) word was then changed by analogy with later borrowings (from Latin), in such cases the sounds subjected to the norms of the French language changed in accordance with the Latin written tradition. Cf. *concentrate* *concenter* (French *concentrer*).

In their further derivational development in the new European language, bookish (derivative) borrowings from Latin demonstrate a number of the most productive models. Our material shows that, most often, adjectives and, to a lesser extent, nouns and verbs act as producers, and the most common derivatives (with a high degree of regularity) are (1) adjective-based nouns with the meaning of an abstract attribute ending in *-ity* element, which was also borrowed from Latin (nouns ending in *-itas*), probably through French *-ité* (*amicability*, *accessibility*, *credibility*, *calculability*, *circularity*, *cordiality*, *criminality*, *perceptibility*, etc.); (2) adjectives ending in *-ive* from the Latin Supinum base (*calculative*, *consultative*, *corporative*, *creative*, *incubative*, *participative*, *perceptive*, *recessive*, etc.); (3) formed from the latter nouns with a German formant *-ness*, denoting abstract quality (*concessiveness*, *exclusiveness*, *perceptiveness*, etc., as well as from adjectives of another composition such as *conconciseness*, *rebelliousness*, etc.). The use of such primordial suffixes as *-less* and *-ful* is much less regular (*accentless*, *artful*, etc.). In addition, from adjectives of Latin origin are regularly formed “hybrid” adverbs with the English formant *-ly*, since neither the suffixes that form adverbs nor the actual adverbs were actually borrowed from classical languages.

In a new language, the process of simplification of the morphological composition in borrowings, that is de-etymology and rethinking of the word form and structure naturally takes place. These result in a partial loss of motivation and loss of the primary meaning, as well as a semantic development not specified by certain components of the word composition, which are motivating in the source language. Cf., in English, the noun *rebellion* does not preserve the meaning of the ‘renewal of the war’, which was unambiguously motivated for Latin speakers; the verb *to circulate* in English has new meanings not related to the idea conferred in the prefix (‘spread, pass, transmit’, i.e. the idea of movement in a certain direction was lost during the semantic expansion).

In observing and discussing the peculiarities of functioning and development of Latin vocabulary in New Latin texts the emphasis is made on derivational innovations and semantic variation as they vividly demonstrate the potential and flexibility of already existing linguistic repertory within the systemic norms. Therefore, the newly coined units or derivatives to name a new realia will be of primary interest.

1) Morphological derivation proper in the examined corpus is represented mostly with derived nominal parts of speech utilizing standard affixes and roots; cases of compound word-building being relatively rare (hereinafter the contexts for the cited lexemes or phrases are included in the Appendix unless given in the text): *interretialis*, e (<rete) – ‘of networks, pertaining to Internet’: *scriptor est ephemeridis interretialis qua numerat narratque de rebus et naufragiis migrantium*; *locus interreticus* – ‘website, online resource’: *Insidiae terroristicae in ferrivia inferna. XIV perierunt, ut a loco interretico “Fontanka.ru” refertur*; *telefonice* (t. dixit ...) - adv. ‘over the phone’: *Telephonice dixit se bene valere...*; *videogramma* – ‘video recording, footage, clip’: *Nuperrime videogramma L minorum divulgavit, ex quo appareret Demetrium Medwedev, primum ministrum, per rete obscurum opes publicas peregre collocasse.*

2) Compound terms are commonly used with the purpose of specification of meaning by forming a complex two-word unit based on standard syntactic models instead of univocal term:

currus ferreus – carriage (in the underground railway): *Secretus pyrobolus pulveris incendiariae DC librarum in curru ferreo paratus erat*; *militia civilis* – police; *administer (negotiis exteris) praepositus* – ‘minister, secretary (of foreign affairs)’ (as head of a government department).

3) Lexical-semantic development (variation) demonstrates several directions of development.

(a) Variation towards specialization of concepts: *rete obscurum* – (criminal) ploy, criminal network; *historicus (rerum recentiorum)* – columnist, commentator, blogger ...*diurnarius et historicus rerum recentiorum Gabriele Del Grande*; *exercitatio navalis* – naval exercise, maritime training; *officina*, ae – enterprise, business (derived from original meaning ‘workshop’, ‘grocery’); *praefectus*, i – mayor (specialization from the more general ‘person in charge’); *Dispensator Facieslibri* – Facebook editor (further development of its original meaning ‘attendant’).

b) Variation towards generalization of meaning: *dux seditionis* (as of a Russian opposition activist, see in) – opposition leader (*seditio*, *ionis* – riot, mutiny, dissention); *procuratrix nuntiorum* – news agency (*procuratrix*, *icis* – ‘agent, manager’): *KCNA, procuratrix nuntiorum Boreocoreana, Martis die scripsit adventum navium pro argumento sibi esse, quanta insolentia Americani Coream Borealem aggredi vellent.*

4) Linguistic calque or loanwords (semantic borrowing):

symbola, ae – share, participation (*Scripsit symbolas in actis sinistrarum partium...*) based on the semantics of Eng. to contribute (as «to contribute a product of one’s intellectual or creative activity»); *resolutio*, *ionis* – ‘resolution, decision’, (while this meaning not recorded in classical Latin period, it appeared as a loan translation from a modern language, exemplifying a phenomenon of reverse borrowing, see discussion further): *Russi resolutioni Consilii Securitatis Nationum Unitarum intercesserunt...*; *identitas*, *atis* – profile, account (e.g. in social networks), which in the classical Latin was not registered in the meaning ‘identity’: *Inscriptionibus in identitate telegrafica (=Telegram)...*; *vis atomica* – an exact translation from English ‘nuclear power’; *automota birota* – two-wheel scooter/moped (a type of vehicle), a morphological calque following the Latin syntactic model.

5) The last and the smallest group of innovations is represented with variation of grammar characteristics of some vocabulary units, which occurs occasionally: *mercior* – as ‘trade, deal in’ (< classical Latin ‘buy’), cf. *rebus publicis popularibus ... mercarentur*. Consider the following context: *Gubernatores suos in eo vituperaverunt, quod in ipso belli tempore cum seditiosis negotiarentur ... cum rebus publicis popularibus ... mercarentur*; *pereo* – ‘to die, to be killed’ (*Militem civilem periiit*) as a case of variation of verb transitivity characteristic (intransitive for transitive).

IV. DISCUSSION: BASIC TRENDS IN COINING «NEW LATIN LEXICON»

The discussion below is based on identified changes of form and shifts in meaning which probably manifest a number of tendencies of subjective nature followed by the authors within the examined New Latin corpus.

In this respect, it is worth starting with the manifestation of the tendency to splitting the term, that is to analytic development, characteristic of many new languages, when the single word term (*univerbum*) is replaced by a compound name or descriptive phrases, cf. an expert, specialist is termed as *peritus rerum* (lit. “experienced in business”). Obviously, in such descriptive innovations the authors rely on stable morphological (syntactic) models. For example, disciplines of primary education in one of the texts were descriptively rendered as *disciplina, qua prima litterarum initia traduntur*, the classical Latin *trivium* in this case was not avoided, probably, because of its undesirable connotative load.

One of the observed ways of denoting new *realia* is a combination of neologism and a unit of “primordial” Latin vocabulary. It should be noted that, attributive combination has become the most common model for constructing such descriptive names, and in such cases it is the classical Latin adjective retaining its direct meaning, in which it was recorded in dictionaries, that becomes the guarantor of the referential “success” of the whole term, including less stable neologisms, cf. newly coined *autocarrum onerarium* for ‘a lorry, truck’ (*onerarius, a, um* was previously recorded in combination with *navis*). Some redundancy of such combinations is explained by the need to specify the referent by way of adding extra reference to its distinctive features and, thus, by linking it to a new, previously non-existing, fragment of reality.

Thus, the reason why the authors of the new Latin texts often prefer descriptive translation instead of using ready-made units of the classical lexicon can probably be the desire to express the content as accurately as possible with the limited means of the language originally developing in another extralinguistic reality which factor may lead the readers to challenge their referential “feasibility”. This circumstance pushes the author to redundancy and verbosity in describing contemporary *realias* and concepts, furthermore, the requirement of unambiguity and completeness in the presentation of news governs the selection of contextual variants of translation from new languages when creating a new Latin text. For example, despite already existing single-word terms *magistratus, us* and *officialis, is*, officials are termed with the phrase *Magistratus publicus*. In the reports about the events in Egypt, during which local emergency forces used the heavy machinery to clear the square after opposition rallies, the author used the name *machina tractoria*, instead of a more concise *univerbum*. Probably, the author thus expanded the reference of this noun, indicating various specific types of modern vehicles used by the police, which can hardly be termed with *lexemes* of classical Latin.

A similar mechanism seems to work when the calque technique is used in coining names for new things: in such loan translation a noun with a similar meaning is used to translate the main component of the phrase from a modern language into Latin, but reinterpreted in the new reality, while the extending attributive component is selected in the target language in its direct meaning: *caupona nocturna* – nightclub (where *caupona, ae* is an equivalent of ‘tavern, inn’), *communes exercitationes bellicae* – joint military exercises (where *exercitatio, ionis* is ‘an exercise, training, experience’). It has to be noted that, along with exact loan translation (*speculatio externa* – ‘external intelligence’, *cuniculus submarinus* – ‘channel under the sea’, *via serica* – ‘the Silk Way’), combinations with the attribute in genitive are also common, for example, *ministerium a rebus exteris* – the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (please, note the specialization of the meaning of *ministerium, i* – ‘service, position’ in classical Latin).

When naming fundamentally new *realias*, authors often resort to the morphological method of formation of new *lexemes* following the classical models, which is naturally accompanied by conceptual rethinking of semantics. Berry picker as an occupation in one of the texts is termed *deceptor* from *decerpo, decerpsi, decerptum* 3 – ‘(1) to catch; 3) pluck; 4) reap/gather’, and smoking – *fumificatio* from *fumifico* 1 – ‘to emit fumes’.

Finally, a couple of opposites tendencies should be analyzed which the authors of this study believe to be based on personal attitudes and linguistic sense of taste rather than the requirements of system norm or communication efficiency.

The first one is the tendency of deliberate “aging” the terminology of Internet news which may occur due to the desire of the New Latin authors to distance themselves as much as possible from new European languages that have largely accepted the Latin general scientific terminology and included in their vocabulary those roots and even whole lexemes that could be used to denote new realities, albeit with inevitable semantic shifts. Instead, the authors translating modern realia in many cases persistently construct new terms and term combinations in place of potentially or even really existing ones, thus departing from the modern material in search for alternatives in classical Latin.

Thus, in the text dedicated to a ceremony of national art awards, sculpture as one of categories is termed *ars figurativa*, while the classical lexicon could suggest a number of lexemes: *sculptura*, *ars fingendi*, given the quoted combination is not entered in dictionaries.

Nevertheless, the cases of “modernization”, the convergence of the vocabulary of new Latin texts and modern languages are also frequent. Composing a Latin text authors use lexemes with roots that were once borrowed into modern languages, have been semantically developing in it but are still close in meaning (and in form) to the words of a modern language: *periodicum*, *i* in meaning ‘magazine’, *interrogantus*, *i m* – journalist who interviews, *nuntium electronicum* – an electronic newsletter / magazine, *usurpator*, *is* - user (computer), *nuclearius*, *a, um* - nuclear (about weapons, security, waste, etc.). This semantic shift in the choice of a name on the basis of elements similar to those familiar for English speakers (though semantically slightly differing) is surely arbitrary and context dependent. In many cases it is caused by a rather small number of contexts, low frequency and reproducibility, given the minimal number of authors and “users” of texts, cf. *bellator*, *oris* – militant, *thug* (in classical Latin – ‘soldier, warrior’) in the following context: *Ordobellatorum in Columbia clandestinorum nomine Fare ducem suum amisit, cum Alfonso Cano, caput eius, impetu militari occisus est*. In some respects, it is possible to distinguish a trend of borrowing in the “reverse” direction – from new languages into New Latin, or back borrowing: in the course of such a process, elements borrowed once from classical or late Latin into new European languages or being the product of the historical development of Latin material in Romance languages are used in the new Latin text as units of the Latin vocabulary, formed in accordance with the structural norms of Latin and included in the syntagmatic relationships. For example, the phrase “security service” – *procuratoria securitatis* (Cf., *Nationales Securitatis Procuratoria Americanorum (NSA)*) is based on the noun and adjective with Latin roots and word-formation elements (*procurator*-), which in this combination function, for example, in modern Portuguese.

If the above examples, based on such international stems, bring the classical text as close as possible to the modern language, which facilitates the perception of news in Latin, in some other cases it is difficult to find an explanation for such a build-up of the dictionary in addition to the established and sufficient classical lexicon. So, in the text of the news reporting on fires in the vicinity of San Francisco, the neighborhoods are termed as *circumiectus*, and firemen – as *vigiles*. Given that the author of these texts is the same person, we can assume that the decisive factor here is the language personality with its individual preferences, language taste and subjectivity of vocabulary selection. Moreover, the realization of these preferences and the implementation of the choice are probably not accidental and are subject to certain strategies of speech behavior, the author’s self-presentation, etc. The definition and description of such strategies requires further research at the textual level.

V. CONCLUSION

With a certain assumption (taking into account the artificial conditions of appearance, arbitrariness of motivation, etc.), the innovations created in New Latin text have the right to exist, albeit not as a fact of language, but as a fact of speech activity, as an element of the word, because they are created in accordance with all the norms and inherent conditions of the linguistic system development: they utilize once productive standard word-formation models together with roots, stems and derivational morphemes actual in modern European languages, they are constructed on the basis of systemic syntactic relations – and most importantly – they are the result of an actual, although simulated, communicative need for a word to name a thing.

Sumarizing the observations of the peculiarities of such modern Latin innovations contrasted with the processes taking part in development of Latin borrowing in English it is possible to identify a number of trends. In developing the newly borrowed elements the English language took the path of both semantic derivation and morphemic formations (using the numerous adopted derivational elements of Latin origin sometimes combined with originally Germanic ones), whereas in the new Latin authors less often resort to word formation as a method of coining new nominations, preferring contextual neologisms, and also to multiword terms (phrases), showing a certain trend for analytism in the naming of realities, thus following similar patterns in the Neo-Romanesque and Germanic languages. At the same time, creators of new Latin text tend to abstain from serious innovations in the already established structure of the Latin word, probably, due to the fact that Latin in this respect offers an extremely rich potential of its advanced repertory for derivational elements and the flexibility of a synthetic language. This resistance to considerable derivational innovations is presumably caused by the rich vocabulary of the classical Latin language with developed derivational nests, and a huge number of already existing derivatives which are at hand for anyone willing to produce a text in Latin.

However, such generalizations can be made with certain limitations, connected with (a) an objectively scanty sample (a small amount of the New Latin 'corpus' material itself), and (b) the "idiolectic" nature of this material, as it is a product of a very narrow circle of individuals who have their own individual preferences (cf. variations in referring to Russian Saint-Petersburg and the Russian President's office - Petropolis / Petrogradum, praeses Russi / Sarmaticus), and who, on the other hand, are rather homogeneous in their sociolinguistic parameters unlike users of a living language.

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Economic Sciences

TO THE QUESTION ABOUT THE FEATURES OF THE LABOR MARKET IN THE TRANSITIONAL ECONOMY

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Abstract:

There is a transitional economy in post socialistic countries today including Russia. The economic model of transitional labour markets corresponds to this special type of economic systems. By now, modern Russia has already completed the transition period of its socio-economic development, from the command economy to a market economy.

Consequently, transitional labor markets, which are an integral part of the transition economy, must become part of the past reality. Therefore, transitional labor markets have completed their existence, and now they are formed as full-fledged labor markets, reflecting the status of a market economy in Russia.

Keywords: Transitional Labour Market, Divergence of Labour Market, Diffusion of Market Institutions.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the typical models of the labor market in the modern world economy is the model of the emerging labor market in a transitive or transitional economy. "In a transition economy, institutional reforms are an important part of the socio-economic reforms carried out in the country and the basic condition for ensuring their effectiveness". The transitive model reflects the features of the economic institution of the labor market at the stage of the formation of market relations. Because of this, the basic principle of its functioning is the contradictory interaction of inertia of old institutional forms and qualitatively new changes in the content of labor relations.

To date, a transitive model of the labor market has developed in countries with a former socialist (command-administrative) economy. These are the countries of Central and Eastern Europe, Belarus and Ukraine, the Russian Federation, Kazakhstan, and the countries of Central Asia: Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan. Obviously, this is a very broad geographically significant economic resource with a large resource potential, including the national economies of the above-mentioned countries.

The substantive patterns of the transitive model are determined not so much by the reform of the economic employment policy and labor market regulation methods, but rather by the transformation of all the components of the social and labor system. The destruction of the stability of old institutional forms and the instability of new forms endow the transitive model of the labor market with a known instability; thus the possibilities of its multivariate development are laid.

The specificity of the labor market model in a country with a transitive economy depends on the choice of a general model for the development of the national economy, the degree of adherence to the existing world analogues, the diversity of specific features in the sphere of labor relations that determine the formation of its own original type of market. The assistance or resistance in the movement of the formation of labor market relations in one direction or another is determined by the potential of the chosen option, real social and economic opportunities, the power of inertia of the past (the influence of institutions), the support or opposition of non-economic factors and even the social ratio political forces in the country, etc. The basic principle of the functioning of the transitive model of the labor market reflects the contradictory interaction of old forms of planned employment and new market changes in the system of labor relations. The form of resolving this contradiction is overcoming the stable but gradually dying features of the planned system of distribution of labor resources by increasing the presence of qualitatively new elements of market relations.

II. METHODOLOGY

The aim of the study is theoretical and methodological analysis and empirical study of the essence, problems, quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the labor market to characterize the prospects for its development within the transition economy.

The subject of the study are the factors that influence the specifics, problems and the state of the labor market in a transitional economy in the country and in the region.

The theoretical and methodological basis for the study was the work of Russian scientists in such branches of social knowledge as the labor market economy. The model of comprehensive research is based on a systematic approach. Of particular importance for the definition of the methodology of this work is the concept of organizing the management of the labor market and the application of effective recruitment technologies, developed in the studies of L.P. Kiyani and others.

III. RESULTS

Elements of the non-market system in a transitive economy are manifested in the presence of non-market regulators in the labor market, the preservation of non-economic coercion to work, the old principles of organization and payment of labor, the stereotypes of labor behavior, adequate for non-market relations, the outdated vocational qualification structure of employment and formal complex training and retraining of personnel, weak mobility of the workforce as a whole.

The situation of wage workers in a transitional economy, which is in the process of transition from a planned (state-guaranteed) employment system to a market system, proves difficult. They are more disunited and disenfranchised towards their employer than this can be observed even in a real market economy. Their labor services, as a rule, are sold at prices below equilibrium in the official labor market. The development of market elements in the transitive model finds expression in the development of the legislative foundations of the labor market, the appearance of various forms of employment, the creation of infrastructure elements, the emergence of methods and means of market regulation, etc. The employment, formed by recruitment plans, real demand for labor. Legislative registration received such phenomena as unemployment and temporary unemployment. Transformation of the traditional turnover of staff in voluntary unemployment or subjective unemployment, the emergence of its forced forms, discourage the discrete nature of employment, and the search for paid work is a type of economic activity of the population.

With the emergence of institutions of private and collective entrepreneurship, the opportunities for choosing conditions for the use of labor are expanding. Competitive beginnings are emerging (in the form of competition for jobs or highly qualified personnel). Transformations also affect the social aspect of labor relations, since institutions for labor mediation, social support for the unemployed are being created, special programs to promote employment are beginning to operate, career counseling and psychological assistance to the unemployed are developing. The nature of labor relations in the transitive model of the labor market is due to technologically backward production, which is characterized by extensive involvement of the labor

force and a low level of actual utilization of labor resources, which forms a backward structure of employment with a low skill inherent in it. The state of production and unfavorable social and industrial working conditions do not provide opportunities for the realization of the educational and qualification potential of the workforce, they focus on low intensity and productivity of labor, indifference to low-value labor. The general trend of production degradation is opposed by elements of modern labor-attraction technologies that form labor relations of a different type-with the predominance of time-based payment, incentives for improving the quality of the workforce. As a result, the differentiated production conditions determine the diversity of the structure of labor relations.

Another reason for the existence of a transitive model of the labor market is the established social traditions inherent in the parties to labor relations. For a long time, countries with a command and administrative economic system were characterized by a traditionally high degree of collectivism, including labor (group solidarity and labor enthusiasm, mutual support of working colleagues, comradely mutual assistance, etc.). This component, as an expression of the national character, must not only be ignored, but maintained in forms compatible with the processes of development of the labor market institution (preservation of the traditions of social and collective labor, support of collective economic interests, etc.). A specific feature of the transitive model of the labor market is due to the totalitarian role of the state in regulating the labor sphere and the existence of such a phenomenon as "paternalism." The mentality that was formed in the socialist social system was combined with the responsibility of the state for the material and spiritual well-being of citizens. It was possible to work only by including in the national system of labor relations, in which wages were fixed in the amount determined by the state plan. In turn, the functions of state-owned enterprises met the social needs of direct production (safety and health, training, etc.), as well as workers and their families (construction and maintenance of housing, children's, medical, health institutions, etc.). The disintegration of this life support system resulted in the loss of habitual life guides, which had a negative impact on the world of work, which was reflected in the decline in the quality of the workforce, the deterioration of the health of workers and their families. Decades of work on obsolete and worn out equipment with poor work organization, asynchronous work schedule, pay regardless of education, qualifications and quality of labor services, in the absence of competition for jobs, have formed the corresponding type of employees whose behavior is poorly consistent with the market transformations. The state's departure from paternalism in the labor market (job security in the form of the constitutional right to work), from purposeful regulation of the sphere of labor relations is replaced by the processes of spontaneous adaptation of the population to the new economic conditions. They manifest themselves in the form of inefficient work, additional employment, the extraction of income from unemployment benefits, side occupations and subsidiary farming, the expansion of employment in the shadow economy, and the growth of marginal unemployment. The interaction of the main labor market subjects in the transitive model is based on the opposition of pursuing social partners, which is a direct consequence of the transformation of the former state-bureaucratic property.

The lack of clear guidelines in the economic policy pursued by the state and the rejection of guaranteed employment, the concentration of most property and property rights in the hands of the administration and state officials, the legalization of criminal property and the secret growth of private property on the basis of the initial accumulation of capital have led to a redistribution of power that determines the goals and employment strategy. The implementation of privatization policy, accompanied, in addition to legal forms, by the stolen state property, weakened the dominant influence of the state on the labor market, and in combination with the strengthening of the economic crisis in the world economy - and the position of the public sector. Objectively, the state shares the interests of both employers and workers. Therefore, it is called upon to exercise arbitration functions to regulate labor relations. This is due to the fact that on the one hand, the rise in prosperity and the growth of the national income of the country, other things being equal, is ensured by increasing the quantity and quality of labor; on the other hand, smoothing the contradictions in wages prevents the emergence of labor conflicts. In the planned economy, the interests of the state as an employer prevail. The prevalence of these interests is also characteristic of a transitive economy, which, given the deteriorating financial and economic situation in the country, is accompanied by a change in tax and social policies, and so on.

Due to the priority of the tasks of restraining inflation as a basis for the development of investment processes and focusing on economic growth at the expense of private investors, the state in employment policy expresses interest in increasing the growth of wages not stimulating inflation. A confirmation of this thesis is the low share of government spending by developing countries on employment policy in the structure of gross domestic product (GDP) in comparison with the developed countries of the world. The proclaimed market freedom of the owner of labor services in the transitive model of the labor market is illusory enough. The liquidation of social guarantees and insufficient social protection encourage employees to set their own goals to preserve and improve social status and material level, which contradicts the interests of the real owners of the transitive economy - financial and credit institutions that concentrate most of their property rights in their hands. The redistribution of property causes the redistribution of national income. The concentration of financial and credit resources exclusively in the financial markets does not stimulate the growth of investment activity in the real sector of the economy (in production), does not contribute to the increase in the production needs of employers in the labor force and the improvement of its quality. In this regard, the opportunities for the sale of labor services, taking into account the quality of human capital and their adequate assessment, are sharply reduced.

The growing needs of the population and rising prices accompanying inflation, with a low level of pay, are not accompanied by an increase in the demand for more productive labor. The relationship between labor activity and earned labor income for most workers loses practical meaning. "The system of incentives in the labor market is distorted by the active use of non-monetary forms of compensation, as a result of which wages lose the function of the main motivational mechanism". Delays in the payment of wages further undermine the foundations of material incentives, necessitating a review of the attitude to work and expedient activities in general. "As a result, wages not only lost their reproductive and stimulating functions, but also significantly degenerated into a kind of social benefit, which is completely unrelated to real results".

In the conditions of sharp differentiation of labor incomes the incentive of professional debt does not work. There is a drop in the prestige of many public professions (doctor, teacher, policeman, etc.). As a result, the formation of market relations in the employment sector occurs in the absence of an adequate motivational mechanism that supports this process. Some elements of the market motivational mechanism (including both material motives, behavioral norms, labor ethics, etc.) are formed only in certain segments of the labor market (for example, in the market of highly qualified specialists with skills not tied to a particular production). As a specific feature of the transitive model of the labor market, its market parameters are deformed. So, wages are formed under the influence of far from economic choice of buyers and sellers of labor services, and state and corporate institutions that closely interact with each other, which is manifested in a wide scale of price discrimination of labor. The genesis of market relations is accompanied by a sporadic development of the naturalization of wages, equalization of wage arrears. The main factors of competition in the transitive model of the labor market are not the costs and prices of labor services, but the level and scope of corporate power over the market, production and social processes, the acquisition of social status. In addition, it should be noted the combination of corporate competition with the preservation of elements of paternalistic care and clan partnership. Transitive labor market model is characterized by diffusion (Latin *diffusio* - distribution, spreading, dispersion) of its characteristic institutions. The institutional framework of the labor market is not clearly defined, the coordination and interaction of its individual elements are low, the role of legal regulation is low. Following the government course of social protection, the employment service was transformed into an organization whose priority is the fight against unemployment. The programs of employment promotion developed by her emphasize projects in favor of socially unprotected categories, the importance of labor mediation institutions, the tasks of increasing the mobility of the released workforce and its competitiveness in the open labor market. As a result, conditions are developing for the expansion of employment relations unregulated by the labor market in the shadow economy-in the sphere of illegal movement of labor outside tax and other state control, hidden forms of the labor market, and so on. The predominantly spontaneous nature of the development of the labor market, its weak organization in a transitive economy are factors that prevent the labor market from responding elastically to external and internal changes. This prevents the timely elimination of the imbalance of supply and demand due to

increased mobility of the workforce, the improvement of its professional and professional structure, the development of norms for the legal regulation of labor relations,

Thus, the main characteristics of the socio-economic conditions that form intra-labor market relationships, suggests that in transitive model reflects the genesis of primitive labor market while preserving features of pre-capitalist relations and deformed market trends. The dependence of the labor market and the social and labor employment system as a whole on changes in production, non-economic factors and the macroeconomic situation a priori determines the subordination of the labor market situation to the policy pursued by the government. As a rule, labor markets developed in the transitive economy do not have legal certainty and socio-economic regulation of labor relations, the quality of which can predetermine the prospects for the transformation process as a whole.

Many market transformations are either only declared or not completed. Their ability, pace, scope and modalities are determined not substance transient needs of the creation of the labor market, and are set based on the understanding of the problems of employment managers at all levels, the course of the political struggle in society, which allow to predict the prospects of future development options. In the conditions of active export of capital and reduction of sources of investment crediting of production, social and labor policy measures aimed at developing and implementing mechanisms that facilitated institutional changes in ownership and structural changes in the economy came on the offensive on labor incomes and redistribution of national income in favor of the largest monopolies, arisen during privatization. These trends block the deepening of market changes in employment. The absence of targets in the labor market policy makes it difficult to assign, select means and actions in the process of its formation, which leads to a lagging behind the objective needs of the development of market elements as manifestations of the laws of market relations in employment. The government lost the monitoring of the situation in the social and labor sphere, limited to occasional campaigns renditions of wages, raising taxes on unregistered businesses, leaving outside the public interest such problems of the labor market, as employment in the informal economy, the criminal and illegal business, which become norms of economic activity.

Delay the necessary political decisions, their adoption under the influence of economic necessity, reflects not only the inconsistency of reform steps, but is a consequence of the impact of various sectorial and regional economic communities, political groups, the aggravation of contradictions between them may complicate the process of further development of the labor market. The social bloc in government structures (ministries of labor, social protection agencies, migration services and employment services, etc.) has virtually no capacity to directly influence the scale of employment and unemployment. Its prerogatives include only regulatory support and operational regulation of specific processes in the labor market. In general, the influence of exogenous labor market factors on the part of their political component does not correspond to the goals and requirements of its formation as an element of the social and labor system. Insufficiency of development is confirmed from the position of the conditions for the formation of the market: the creation of a multitude of actors expressing demand and supply is not accompanied by their independence; the behavior of economic entities has no market motivation; the degree of their potential mobility is low; paternalism in social relations hampers the development of competitive principles of the labor market. The labor market has developed in transitive economy is not able to fully perform its attributive function and therefore acts as a deformed microeconomic system with a low threshold of reliability, which results in the creation of a fundamentally non-homogeneous, non-equilibrium in its state of the market, with the inevitable distortions (see the table 1) which predetermines the instability of the labor market system. Since the labor market is in the stage of its institutional development, the links of continuity in its system are more stable. The changes that are taking place do not find enough supporters, and because of the loss of stable employment and lack of motivation, they are accompanied by passive resistance. Hence, according to the created conditions of functioning and its internal properties, the transitive state of the labor market should be characterized as a low-efficiency system. The increase in efficiency is possible in connection with the programmatic development of the labor market system. The effective work of labor markets presupposes the systematic nature of their formation, which includes the definition of strategic development goals, the resources needed to achieve them, and policies aimed at the formation and use of these resources through tactical means. These elements, arranged by the procedures of social technology, enable the managing

structures to carry out purposeful activities to form integrated components of the labor market. To make the process of forming the labor market in a transitive economy dynamic:

1. Economic conditions in which the dominant motive of the owners' behavior will be the development of production and the improvement of quality and labor productivity, which in turn is based on the ability of production structures to dynamics and adaptation;

2. Political conditions in which the organizationally organized coalition of supporters of structural changes in the sphere of employment will carry out the necessary reform (labor remuneration, etc.). In our opinion, the main content of the historical process of the formation and development of the labor market in a transitive economy is the creation of structural changes that lead to the transformation of labor relations, the reform of economic policies and methods for regulating the income of the population.

Table 1. Disproportions of the transitive labor market model

INCOMPATIBILITY IN THE LOCATION OF PARTS OF THE LABOR MARKET	DESCRIPTION OF THE PHENOMENON	CAUSES OF THE PHENOMENON
1. The gap between the demand and supply of skilled workers in quantitative and qualitative terms.	Insufficient supply of workers in construction specialties, drivers of vehicles and installations, workers in housing and communal services and light industry.	In the structure of the economy, the leading positions are occupied by the branches of machine building, chemical industry, and electric power industry.
2. The gap between the demand and supply of specialists in the agro-industrial complex.	Insufficient supply of such specialists, as agronomists, machine operators, livestock breeders, veterinarians.	The underdevelopment of the socio-cultural sphere in the countryside (in any case, its lagging behind the city); low pay.
3. An overabundance of specialists in the financial, economic and legal fields.	Insufficient demand for economists, including accountants, financiers, and lawyers.	The popularization of higher education disrupts the balance of training of specialists at various levels of education: overproduction of specialists with higher professional education.
4. Increased tax burden on the able-bodied population.	Dynamics of the ratio of able-bodied and disabled people.	Negative demographic trends; when external imbalance is met (attracting migrants), the qualitative inconsistency of education levels.
5. Youth unemployment.	The labor market requires professionals with experience and experience of 3 to 5 years.	Low competitiveness of graduates of most universities; The labor market is characterized by an excessive supply of highly qualified specialists.
6. Rural unemployment.	Territorial discrepancy between the volume of vacancies and supply of labor.	Underdevelopment of the regional economy and infrastructure in rural areas; absence of vacant jobs.

IV. CONCLUSION

Thus, the consequence of the specifics of the transitive economy is the emergence of a special model of the labor market, characteristic of the developing countries of the world. Indeed, the labor markets of developed and developing countries are quite seriously different in terms of the level of development of competition, the level of wages as the prices of labor (labor services) and are divided into different segments, sharply differentiated by basic parameters.

Transitive labor markets can deviate to a different degree from the matrix (in Latin, matrix means: a sample, a template, a basis) of developed labor markets, for example, Western European countries.

"The modified content of the labor market is manifested in its new characteristics of behavior and properties". In this case, there is a divergence phenomenon (from the Latin *divergo* - deviate) of the labor market, that is, the divergence of certain features and properties in this economic institution in the course of evolution.

In order not to deviate from the trunk vector of the development of civilization and form full-fledged labor markets, to increase the public prestige of labor, it is necessary to radically change the place of labor market problems in the system of priorities of the state social and economic policy of developing countries, to increase financing for activities related to the solution of the macroeconomic problem of employment and employment of the population.

In this direction, "it is required to eliminate legislative and regulatory gaps in regulating the conjugation of economic opportunities of the state and the realization of the right to work by its citizens". It is also necessary to bring regulatory legal acts, including the Basic Laws (Constitutions) of developing countries in full conformity with international notions of social and economic human rights and take into account the documents of the International Labor Organization (ILO), regulating market processes in sphere of labor and employment of the population.

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Economic Science

MODELS OF THE LABOUR MARKET AND THEIR FEATURES IN THE WORLD ECONOMY

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Abstract:

We distinguish several different and basic for the world economy labour market models. These models are as follows, namely: 1. Liberal model of the labour market (Great Britain and the USA); 2. Socially oriented model of the labour market (Germany and Sweden); 3. National-traditional model of the labour market (Japan and South Korea); 4. Transit model of the labour market (countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), including Russia, and the countries of Central and Eastern Europe (CEE), former socialist countries).

Keywords: Labour Market, Types of Labour Market in a World Economy, Transitional Labour Market.

I. INTRODUCTION

The formation and development of the labour market in the Russian economy is determined not only by its own laws of the market, but also by specific substantive laws that stem from the features of the national model and that space-time continuum within which this model develops. In our opinion, the basis for the study of labour markets can be a historical-typological method. The typology of labour markets cannot be reduced to the concepts of effective and inefficient, full and incomplete employment. Only the unity and interrelationship of socio-economic, regulatory, managerial, organizational and other characteristics can determine the factors and target direction of the development of the labour market institution in a particular country (economy).

The change in the social forms of labour and managerial activity, which is based on fundamental changes in the object-subject interaction, is what truly determines the specifics of certain types of the market that set all its main parameters. This predetermines the logic of finding the patterns of the Russian labour market, dictated by the subordination of economic features of the general civilization process of development of the market sphere of employment with the laws of the process of genesis of market relations.

II. METHODOLOGY

According to world experience, various ways of developing a market economy are refracted in the sphere of employment in specific economic models of labour markets. The formation of this or that model is conditioned by the general typology of the market economy, within which the labour market mechanism functions, and depends on the choice of priorities in the national economy, based on the specifics of its socioeconomic development and the degree of involvement in the world economy. Such a methodological approach to the study of labour markets will allow us to assess not only the impact of macroeconomic development on the nature of labour relations, but also to substantiate the opportunities and directions of their development. The predominance of certain features in the model, determined by historical, institutional, national and other conditions, makes it possible to classify the type of relations formed in them into several basic models of the labour market.

1. Liberal model of the labour market (Great Britain and the USA);
2. Socially-oriented model of the labour market (Germany and Sweden);
3. National-traditional model of the labour market (Japan and South Korea);
4. Transit model of the labour market (countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), including Russia, and the countries of Central and Eastern Europe (CEE), former socialist countries).

In the first models inherent in countries with developed market economies, the national labour market acts as a link in the international labour market. It is distinguished by the legislative equality of employers and employees; the emphasis on the quality characteristics of the labour force in competition, the payment of labour services is equivalent to their quality, level of education and qualifications, rotation of jobs. The necessary conditions for the functioning of labour markets in these models are the provision, at the expense of minimal time wages, of a standard of living higher than the subsistence minimum, the development of a system of training and retraining of personnel, and other market structures (in particular, the housing market). At the same time, distinctions between them on basic characteristics are clearly visible. Realizing concrete theoretical models, real labour markets are characterized by sufficient variability, which reflects in their functioning the dynamics of national, political, economic, socio-cultural, ideological development. This is confirmed by the analysis of the most typical models.

III. RESULTS

1. Liberal model of the labour market (Great Britain and the USA).

This model is a liberal market-capitalist model that assumes the priority role of private property, a market-competitive mechanism, capitalistic motivations, a high level of social and economic differentiation (the classic example of this model is the United States of America). The American labour market was formed as a set of labour and administrative resources that perform various functions in the field of employment. Resources are not only the personnel themselves, but also state programs that finance in the field of training and retraining of personnel, migration movements, social protection of various social strata of society. The current programs are aimed at various social strata of American society and the implementation of specific goals in the field of employment (public spending on these programs is about \$ 300 billion annually in the form of various donations for social support, training and retraining). The labour market in the USA fixes the differentiation of the main spheres of employment: 1. Low-paid jobs, for which workers with low qualifications are required; 2. Workplaces with high requirements for the qualification of workers and, accordingly, with high wages; 3. Workplaces that provide high wages, with low qualification requirements (work in production shops in the assembly). In the current structure of workplaces, an intensive rotation process is observed, under the influence of which the labour market polarization is formed. There is a redistribution of jobs in favor of more skilled work, while reducing jobs for low-skilled workers. Annually in the United States, 10-15% of all jobs are updated with a constant increase in the sector of highly skilled labour (50-60% of all vacancies are occupied by managers and specialists).

At the same time, the number of jobs with low skills of employed people is declining, for which labour productivity is low. The number of vacancies with a higher level of requirements for employees is increasing. Every year in the US industry, up to 10% of jobs are reduced and 9% of new jobs are created that require workers of higher qualifications. The reduction in jobs in production is, to some extent, compensated by the creation of new jobs in the service sector (out of 10 million jobs created by the US administration over the past few years, up to 80% are for the service sector). Today, the American model of the labour market does not cope with the growth of the supply of labour, in connection with which the flow of the able-bodied population forced to seek work abroad increases. In the dynamics of the demand for labour, the requirements to the quality of the labour force are increasing, characteristic for both material production, where the proportion of skilled workers is traditionally higher, and for the service sector. This is essential for changing the structure of employment. Indirect evidence of the convergence of the qualifications structures of the two most important spheres of the economy is the narrowing of the gap in the average salary (if in the 1980s the gap between the average weekly wages in industry and services was \$ 80, then in the 1990s it fell 4 times).

The increase in the scale of highly skilled labour in the sphere of non-material production leads to the fact that they cannot occupy the released low-skilled labour, as it was before. The result of the strengthening of the labour market segmentation is the additional difficulties of finding employment for groups of the population who do not have sufficient qualifications. For example, for long-term unemployed, whose level is 45-50% among all the unemployed, or the black population of the country, unemployment rates are three times higher than the national average. The aggravation of employment problems is due to the implementation of a new employers' labour market strategy (reducing labour costs by restraining staff salaries as the main means of increasing product competitiveness). Among the ways to reduce high labour costs, one should note the curtailment of certain social obligations (in particular, medical, pension insurance). Recently, the share of large and medium-sized companies with health insurance of their employees has decreased by 15% and amounted to 75%, while pension insurance companies have decreased from 63% to 57%, in small companies 69% and 20%, respectively. The logical consequence of this policy is lengthening the duration of the working week and overtime hours employed. This trend indicates a deviation from the idea of reducing the duration of working hours as a means of reducing unemployment. Another manifestation of the policy of reducing labour costs and reducing unemployment is the expansion of the labour of partially jammed and temporary workers. $\frac{1}{3}$ all created jobs are intended for temporary workers. However, the introduction of flexible forms of employment also does not find unconditional support in modern conditions. There are growing concerns about the loss of incentives for entrepreneurs to invest in the development of human capital due to excessive labour mobility.

As an important trend of the US labour market, we should note the strengthening of the motivational dominance for hired workers in the growth of qualifications, which can be traced both in pay and in the relationship between education and the position of workers in the market. If 20 years ago graduates of higher educational institutions of the USA received 50% more than school leavers did, now this gap exceeded 83.5%. Above all, the unemployment rate among those who did not finish school is half that among school leavers, among those having higher education - no more than 1.5%. Increasing the competitiveness of workers in the labour market is seen as one of the nationwide goals of improving the living standards of Americans, which is reflected in the emerging trend in the increase in public employment policies of its active elements associated with the costs of organizing training and retraining, the selection of jobs, and public funding work places.

The methods used in the American model to contain labour costs, rotate jobs, increase labour market flexibility, and stimulate active government policies show a rejection of macroeconomic stimulation of aggregate demand as a means of expanding employment and are a manifestation of the search for new approaches in employment policy. The development of the American labour market, taking place within the framework of the liberal model, in modern conditions reflects attempts to exit the country from the crisis zone, characterized by a reduction in the number of jobs and rising unemployment.

2. Socially-oriented model of the labour market (Germany and Sweden). It is a social democratic model that assigns the role of the supreme social and economic power to the state (the Swedish model). The

model is based on the Institute of Social Insurance. The emergence of the social insurance system in Sweden dates back to the early 20th century. During its existence - especially in the period after the Second World War - this system has undergone significant modifications. Its main feature is universality. In its orbit is every Swedish citizen, regardless of the occupation, and in many cases and on whether or not this person receives wages. This state of affairs is referred to in Sweden as a "universal social policy". Over the past few decades, the size of social insurance as a whole has increased. However, due to the economic difficulties of recent years, individual rates have been reduced, and in some cases the conditions giving the right to receive benefits have been more rigidly defined. However, the principle of universality remained the same. Now, the social security system in Sweden has entered a phase of rapid change. Parliament approved the law on a new old-age pension system; reforms of disability pensions and benefits to families without a breadwinner are planned. Organization of social insurance system. State insurance companies take decisions on the allocation of a benefit other than unemployment benefits at the local level. The State Insurance Fund and its regional offices are available in each region. Such cash desks do not have their own funds and accordingly do not take any part in direct financing. Collection of funds for social benefits is carried out through the collection of taxes. The social insurance centres are subordinate to the State Social Insurance Administration ("Riksförserkringverkverket"), which has the right to make certain decisions and recommendations. At the governmental level, the Ministry of Social Protection is responsible for legal and budgetary issues related to social insurance. Issues related to unemployment benefits are under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Labour.

Democratically elected state authorities are delegated huge powers to regulate social and economic life. However, we cannot but admit that the conceptual differences between the social market economy and "Scandinavian socialism" are being eroded in practice. Thus, modern countries have taken a course to build a socially regulated market economy, which underlies the concept of "mixed farming system". The Swedish labour market has a smaller capacity compared to the US market (it has a total of 4.3 million jobs for 8 million people, of which 800-900 thousand are annually released, and the level of rotation of staff is 20% per year). With a high degree of employment of men (86%) and women (81%), the unemployment rate in this labour market averaged in 1961-70. - 1,7%, 1971-80 years. - 2.1%, 1981-90. - 2.5%, in 1991-2000. - 7.5%.

Satisfaction of demand for jobs is ensured in the labour market by a set of measures that in many respects make up the functioning of the Swedish economy. It is based on a wide range of social and economic activities.

1. Ensuring sufficient consumer demand for goods and services;
2. Providing enterprises with an opportunity for profitable work and maintaining competitiveness in the world market for the preservation and increase of jobs within the country;
3. Effective functioning of labour exchanges;
4. Maintaining a balanced proposal (through an advanced system of retraining and stimulating entrepreneurial activity as self-employment) and demand for labour (laws on youth, disabled people);
5. Unemployment Insurance;
6. Containment of inflation;
7. Provision of housing guarantees when moving to a new place of work;
8. Raising awareness of the work community about vacancies.

Social programs within this labour market model characterize relatively high public expenditures, in which up to 70% are directed to means of active protection of the population in the labour market. The cost of employment policies in Sweden is about 2.2-2.7% of GDP against 0.8% in the USA.

In an active employment policy designed to facilitate the rapid inclusion of released workers in labour, measures are dominated by the impact on the structure and qualitative characteristics of the workforce (vocational guidance, vocational training and retraining programs, promotion of labour mobility), the regulation of labour demand by measures to support employment (in including public works programs, job segregation, etc.). For the provision of material assistance to the unemployed, only used financial resources are spent. In achieving social consensus, great importance is attached to collective contractual regulation of wages and the linkage of its growth with an increase in labour productivity, the balance of interests of market actors in the so-called social wage issues. It should also be noted the significant role of

trade unions in supporting employment security. Social orientation of labour relations gives this model an attraction from the standpoint of collectivist mentality and state guarantees of employment. However, at the same time, it reflects an inability to modify production and has less competitiveness compared to the liberal type. In addition, strong social guarantees form the passive behaviour of workers in the labour market. This finds expression, in particular, in the increase in the proportion of the unemployed with long periods of unemployment.

The German model is a model of a social market economy, which is linked to the expansion of competitive principles with the creation of a special social infrastructure that mitigates the shortcomings of the market and capital, with the formation of a multi-layered institutional structure of subjects of social policy. In the German economic model, the state does not set economic goals - this lies in the plane of individual market decisions - but will create reliable legal and social framework conditions for the implementation of the economic initiative. Such framework conditions are embodied in civil society and the social equality of individuals (equality of rights, starting opportunities and legal protection). They actually consist of two main parts: civil and economic law, on the one hand, and a system of measures to maintain a competitive environment, on the other. The most important task of the state is to ensure a balance between market efficiency and social justice. The treatment of the state as a source and defender of the legal norms regulating economic activity and competitive conditions does not go beyond the limits of the Western economic tradition. But the state's understanding of the German model and, in general, the concept of a social market economy differs from the state's understanding of other market models by the idea of a more active state intervention in the economy. The following features characterize the German model, which combines the market with a high degree of state interventionism. First, individual freedom as a condition for the functioning of market mechanisms and decentralized decision-making. In turn, this condition is provided by an active state policy of maintaining competition. Secondly, social equity - the market distribution of income is due to the amount of capital invested or the amount of individual efforts, while the achievement of relative equality requires vigorous social policies. Social policy is based on the search for compromises between groups that have opposite interests, as well as on the direct participation of the state in the provision of social benefits, for example, in housing construction.

Third, anticyclical regulation and stimulation of technological and organizational innovations; implementation of structural policy. Fourthly, the protection and promotion of competition. These features of the German model are derived from the fundamental principles of the social market economy, the first of which is the unity of the market and the state. This is a model of regulated corporate capitalism, in which favourable opportunities for capital accumulation are combined with the active role of state regulation in the areas of programming economic development, structural, investment and foreign economic policy and with the special social significance of the corporate principle. Expanding the functions of the state in modern society while preserving market freedoms, institutions and mechanisms is to a decisive extent due to the increased complexity of the social and economic process. Many of the fundamental problems of today's society can not be effectively addressed by market mechanisms alone. This is primarily the strengthening of the social sphere, which has become one of the most important sources of economic growth. Thus, the level of education, the qualification of the workforce and the state of scientific research directly affect the pace and quality of economic growth, which is confirmed by econometric calculations. A huge impact on the quality of the labour force, on economic development in general, is provided by health care, social security and the state of the environment. The market itself can not create a powerful social sphere, although market mechanisms, especially competition, may have a strong social orientation. Therefore, a socially oriented market economy is aimed at fulfilling both economic and non-economic goals, using a wide range of economic and social policy instruments. In general, these goals can be formulated as follows:

- ensuring economic growth and economic stability;
- social security and social justice;
- promoting competition • ensuring political stability.

In the mixed economy, the economic mechanism undergoes substantial changes. Planned methods of management are further developed within the framework of individual firms in the form of a marketing management system. At the same time, at the macro level, the development of planned methods is

connected with the state regulation of the economy. The planned approach is a means of actively adapting to the requirements of the market. As a result, the key tasks of economic development are given a new solution. Thus, the issue of the volume and structure of products is solved on the basis of market research within firms, as well as analysis of priority directions of NTP, the forecast of development of social needs at the macro level. The market forecast allows reducing in advance the output of obsolete goods and passing to qualitatively new models and types of products. The marketing system of production management makes it possible to bring individual costs of companies producing the bulk of goods of this type to the socially necessary costs even before production begins. State sectorial and national programs (plans) also have a significant impact on the volume and structure of goods and services produced, ensuring their greater compliance with changing public needs. The task of using resources is solved within the framework of large companies based on strategic planning taking into account the most promising sectors. At the same time, the redistribution of resources for the development of the newest branches takes place at the expense of budgetary appropriations, state national and interstate programs; research and development work in the priority areas of the scientific and technological revolution.

Finally, the task of distributing the created gross national product is decided not only based on traditionally established forms, but also supplemented by the allocation of ever greater resources by both large companies and the state for investments in the development of the "human factor".

These activities are financing of education systems, including retraining of workers of various qualification, improvement of medical services for the population, social needs. At least 30-40% of all state budget allocations in developed countries with a market economy are currently channelled into social security, the implementation of numerous "poverty alleviation" programs.

3. National-traditional model of the labour market (Japan and South Korea). A distinctive feature of this model of the labour market is its orientation on the protection of employment, provided that the employees meet certain performance standards, which reflects the commitment to national traditions. For hired workers, high guarantees of stable employment are the main factor in motivating to work and achieving personal success. For employers, an important form of motivation is their ability to fulfil their obligations to employees. The stability of employment also affects the readiness to adapt to changes, since the latter do not associate with the loss of jobs. The mobility of staff in the model is quite high, but it is not horizontal, but vertical. All this requires the interaction of the government, administration and trade unions. The main factors of consolidation between labour and capital are the adoption of decisions on social issues on the basis of consensus, the transfer of solutions of specific social issues to the level of enterprises on the basis of the recommendations of laws and government decrees, the awareness of employees about the problems and incomes of the firm. In the income policy, the formation of the labour strategy is based on the socially oriented concept of labour productivity. It provides for the distribution of income between entrepreneurs and workers, depending on the degree of participation in their education, an annual increase in the base rate, salary based on a collective agreement, weighted differentiation in earnings between employees of different levels, etc. The preference given to the human factor in combination with the workers' confidence in maintaining stable employment about effectiveness to successful progress on the path of productivity growth. Another characteristic feature of the model under consideration is the formation of an employment policy on a planned basis. At the legislative level, long-term and annual employment plans are developed, which serve as guidelines for practical activities at the prefectural level.

The main objectives of these plans are to help stabilize employment when changing economic structure, to respond to changes in employment (such as aging of society, foreign labour inflow, increase in the number of working women, etc.). Particular attention is paid to the promotion of lifelong learning for the development of professional abilities, the reduction of working hours, the expansion of social protection measures for citizens in need of special care. Because of directed economic expansion in Japan, the number of job offers could exceed the number of job seekers. A significant increase in the number of employers in Japan has led to a low percentage of unemployed workers. In these conditions, an increasing number of companies, mainly from small and medium-sized businesses, are experiencing a shortage of workers. Serious problems for the country are the employment of middle-aged and elderly people, as well as the imbalance of supply and demand in various regions of Japan and professional groups. One of the trends

is a decrease in the number of jobs for older age groups and an increase in the number of unemployed older workers.

Because of the concentration of demand for the labour force of young people, unemployment of the latter does not represent a social problem for this labour market model. The Law on Stabilization of Employment of Senior Citizens covers the middle and older people, according to which 90% of companies use the system to ensure the age limit of employment of workers. As part of promoting employment of older persons, it is possible to resume work, develop part-time employment, etc.

IV. CONCLUSION

In the current conditions of the aging of society, the importance of acquiring employment and developing the professional abilities of young people. Special measures are aimed at promoting women's employment. The system by which general regulation of the labour market is achieved in this model includes employment centres, training schools for working people, and measures of social assistance for the unemployed. All these issues are under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Labour and prefectures, which in their employment and retraining issues operate on their territories independently. The economic entities themselves, that is, enterprises (firms), are engaged in the employment of the liberated workers of large enterprises.

As for the transitional model of the labour market, it generally lacks a generally accepted national concept for the development of the labour market, while in developed economies these concepts exist. For example, the proclamation of a "full employment policy" in the United States, "equal opportunities" and "social partnership" in Sweden and Austria serves as the ideological basis for the employment policies pursued in these countries. Today, employment policies and the fight against unemployment in labour markets are an important part of state policy in all countries of the world, including Russia.

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Historical Sciences

THE RUSSIAN CHURCH IN THE STATE MECHANISM OF RUSSIA

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Abstract:

In article outlines the key areas of the charitable and educational activities of the Orthodox Church, which are analyzed during religious reforms in the 19th and early 20th centuries. in Russia. It is shown that at that time the scale of charity aid and the responsibilities of charitable organizations increased; the control over the distribution of aid has improved, the role of the Church in the social protection of the population has increased.

The conclusions made in the article allow us to look at a holistic picture of the Church's activities in providing the educational process in Russian church schools during the period under study. It turned out that the concrete activity of the clergy, which was impossible without the proper level of education, placed the clergy in the most literate category of the population.

It is the priests, in the absence of a developed education system in Russia, began to introduce primary public education. This article helps to understand and systematize the position of the Church as a spiritual and moral institution that preserves Russia's cultural heritage. Of particular importance is the regional nature of the topic under study, which makes it possible to understand the general and specific relations between the Church and the state. For the international community, the article will be useful as an archival exhibition, which is a rare publication that reveals the relationship between the Orthodox Church and the state in Russia in the 19th and early 20th centuries.

Keywords: Church, state, priest, charity, hierarchy.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the XIX - early XX centuries. The Orthodox Church occupied an important place in the life of the Russian people. Priest A. Borisov spoke about the influence of the Church: "The existence of the Russian Orthodox Church was for people a sign of the presence of God in the world". The social role and functions of religion in the XIX century have changed a lot. The church was represented as a natural institution that plays

a huge role in human life, raising spirituality over social, aesthetic and economic values. Due to significant changes in the country, relations between the church and the state have created new trends.

The role of the Church began to prevail not only in the socio-cultural, but also in the political life of the Russian state. The Christian ideology of the Orthodox Church influenced the consciousness of Russian citizens. The Russian Orthodox Church is able to cultivate in a person such qualities as love for people, patience, compassion, mercy, honesty, modesty, respect for the interests of others, which constitutes the spiritual basis of the individual. An objective assessment of any event can not be given without a complete picture of the interaction of the Church and the state. In this regard, the Church can be described as a social organization.

On the one hand, the Church was a collection of communities, and on the other hand, it was a church hierarchy. In the modern era, the Church organically joined the civil society. Being a part of civil society, the Church has always been independent of the state and even competed with the state not only in the social sphere, but also in the spiritual sphere. Religion is the spiritual component of the Church. The ontology (the picture of the world) and the axiology (value system) offered by religion differed from the ideology of the state. Since the Church has always relied on tradition, it has been perceived as "eternal" and unchanging, beginning with its origins, and therefore it was an alternative to a "changing" world.

The Church professed the image of the fidelity of tradition. Cultural beliefs, symbols and values were a sphere of religion, and they solved questions of human existence. Analyzing these historical facts, one can understand the particular urgency of this topic.

II. METHODOLOGY

The methods used in the article are traditional for historical works. In order to analyze the relationship between the Church and the state, a systematic method was used to comprehensively study the concepts and ideas of different scientists in order to compare these concepts with each other and emphasize their interrelationship and role.

The process of relations between the Church and secular power in positive and negative development can be analyzed using the method of scientific objectivity and historicism, which made it possible to reveal that in the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries the incorporation of the Orthodox Church into the state administration of the Russian state was practically completed. The article uses a comparative-historical method that makes it possible to trace the development of Orthodoxy in Russia's public life, to show the features of the formation of the Church and society as a whole during this period. One can single out the method of synchronization, which makes it possible to trace the history of the development of missionary fraternities in the region, to reveal the peculiarities of their work, which consists in the opening of schools, libraries, reading rooms, sobriety societies. Another important method used in this article was the statistical method.

The statistical method allowed to confirm the results that were made when analyzing numerous unpublished and published materials. The digital data used in the article were taken from the materials of federal and regional archives. On the basis of information on the activities of the church and state structures contained in the archives, one can get a fairly clear idea of the number and financial condition of the parishes, the dynamics of the opening of churches and monasteries.

The method of socio-psychological analysis made it possible to show the reasons for the activation of large masses of the population in the sphere of people's donations to the construction of Orthodox churches. This method also revealed the fact that the Church served as an important link in the social assistance system. The actualization method, based on the analysis of the results obtained, made it possible to make some forecasts and develop practical recommendations that would help solve the problems in the relations between the church and the state at the present time.

The use of different approaches and methods of scientific research made it possible to create a clear picture of the relationship between the state and the Church in the 19th and early 20th centuries. in Russia.

III. RESULTS

The Orthodox Church in the XIX century was an instrument of state policy, an institution that merged with state structures. The church was ruled by the Holy Synod and spiritual consistories. Although the Synod was an executive power and had no legislative initiative, he issued orders, which were to be performed by the spiritual departments. The composition of the Synod has changed, but in the XIX - early XX centuries. There were 10 bishops representing the black clergy, as well as the confessor of the emperor and the chief priest of the army and navy, who were representatives of the white clergy. Some members of the Synod were permanent, who were obliged to attend all meetings of the Synod: for example, the confessor of the emperor, the chief priest of the army and navy, Metropolitan of St. Petersburg; The temporary members took part in the Synod meetings once or twice a year.

The spiritual consistories were headed by bishops, they were appointed by the Synod and the emperor. The bishop, together with the spiritual consistory and with the support of the dean - the senior priests in the diocese - exercised administration and the court. The members of the spiritual consistory were representatives of the white and black clergy, who were elected bishop. As part of the consistories, the white clergy were represented better than in the Synod: in 1801 the parish priests accounted for 38% in the consistory, and in the 1860s. - 79%. The emperor himself supervised the work of the Chief Prosecutor of the Synod. But the control of the chief prosecutor was superficial, and therefore the spiritual consistories were controlled independently. The development of the institute of the Ober-Procuracy can be divided into two phases: the first - from the day of its appearance until 1803 the second phase began in 1817 and lasted until 1803-1817. until the end of the Synodal period.

Until 1803, the influence of the Chief Prosecutor had no decisive role in the work of the Synod, which was in direct contact with the emperor himself. Monasteries were ruled by monks. At the beginning of the reign of Alexander I the Synod consisted of five representatives of the black clergy. This composition was created by Catherine II. The church was one of the state ministries - "the ministry of Orthodox confession" - throughout the entire imperial period of Russian history. The Emperor received various proposals on the reform of the Church with regard to changing various aspects of her life. The highest political leadership understood that church reforms are necessary, and the emperor and his entourage are interested in strengthening Orthodoxy. In this connection, the experience of the General Directorate of Spiritual Affairs of Foreign Confessions and the Ministry of Spirituality and National Education is of great interest.

The experience of creating such a double ministry was to include church authorities in the state structure, thereby realizing many ideas through education. The initiator of the creation of these state institutions was the supreme power of the state in the person of Emperor Alexander I and his closest assistants, among whom the most important role in this process was played by A.N. Golitsyn, who was an active supporter of the inclusion of church authorities in state structures. In the difficult conditions of Russia's renewal, the clergy attempted to assume the role of an independent moral arbiter, insisting on overcoming class differences and appeasing social upheavals. The state of the church and state in Russia at the end of the nineteenth century was as follows: the Orthodox Church was deprived of independence because of custody and control over the state; disagreement in religion was brutally suppressed. However, the unification of the Church and the state was a boon for both sides, as it allowed each side to fully use its reserves for a dignified life.

Thus, summing up, it can be noted that the connection between the Church and the state was built in the XIX - early XX centuries. on the principle of subordination of the Church to state power. In fact, the Orthodox Church was one of the divisions of a ramified state apparatus. The emperor was the bearer and source of supreme authority in the Orthodox Church. The church was under the tutelage of state power, without a real possibility to act as an independent spiritual and moral force. However, it was a public legal institution that performed such functions as collection of statistical data, registration of acts of civil status, control over spiritual censorship and administration of justice. In addition, the Church was responsible for public education.

IV. DISCUSSION

Historiography of the problem of the relationship between the Russian Orthodox Church and the state in the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. is divided into pre-revolutionary, Soviet and post-Soviet periods. In the pre-revolutionary period secular and ecclesiastical historians conducted significant work on the collection of materials and their publication. Basically, these materials had the nature of reference data and historical essays.

The content of some of them is still relevant today. In their studies, scientists talked about the difficulties of the parish clergy and tried to attract public attention to it. Historian P.V. Znamensky in his book studied the position of the clergy in the XIX century. He analyzed the legislation on the Church and played an important role in public events with regard to the clergy. P.V. Znamensky mainly studied materials on the central and southern dioceses. Historian D.I. Rostislavov analyzed the complex material situation of the clergy in his works, he was one of the first who drew attention to the incomes of clergymen and their economic activities. He paid considerable attention to the monastic economy.

Work D.I. Rostislavova presents statistics on 290 monasteries. Historian P.N. Miliukov believed that the role of the Church and its social position depended on state power, the clergy was a closed class, and the believers were satisfied with sectarianism and the Old Believers. Mirsky devoted his work to the problems of the white clergy. It is noteworthy that the author tried to protect the moral state of the clergy in the eyes of society. He spoke about the need to transfer priests to the state salary. In the pre-revolutionary period, a lot of literature on the history of church law was published. Among these works is allocated IG. Aivazov about the activities of the Orthodox faith during the reign of Emperor Alexander III and church-civil orders. These works contain information about the rights to clerical rights and their rights to use land. In the Soviet period of research on the history of the Russian Orthodox Church there was little. For the study of religion and the Church, the approach was ideological. The clergy turned out to be the exploiter of people. In the literature on the history of the Church during the Soviet period, tendentiousness prevailed, the pathos of denunciation prevailed, facts were often distorted.

Despite the prevalence of publicism in the evaluation of church activity, scientific methods based on historical material are gradually beginning to penetrate. In the 1920s. the first generalizing studies on the history of the Church are published, in which some aspects of his activity in Soviet Russia were touched upon. Titlinov's work was more impartial. On the whole, the author examined the situation of the Russian Orthodox Church impartially, noting that the diocesan authorities did not care much for their moral obligations during the monarchical period, in fact being one of the structures of the power system that was expressed in the negative attitude of the clergy to the religious policy of the state. In Candidov's work "The Church and 1905" was given a significant source material, which allowed to identify the relationship of the tsarist regime with the Orthodox clergy. In the opinion of B.P. Candidova, in general, the activity of the church was counter-revolutionary in nature, most priests persistently supported the autocracy. This work had a vivid political connotation. The main work of the Soviet historian V.I. Pisareva gives an objective assessment of the activities of the Orthodox Church in the Russian state. The author made conclusions about the crisis of the Church, about the increase in the Church's interference in state affairs, about the growth of the material welfare of the clergy. IN AND. Pisarev believed that the reforms of the 1860s lifted class restrictions in the formation of the clergy and changed the professional training of the clergy.

Most modern scholars objectively approach the study of the history of the Orthodox Church. B.N. Mironov published a monograph "The Social History of Russia in the Period of the Empire", in which he examines the formation and development of the clergy in Russia. He believes that the spiritual state in Russia is completely independent in the state system. B.N. Mironov shows how the clergy from the estate turned into a professional group. These works contain various information about the history of the state and the Church. Some of these studies have a narrow topic, while others are limited to a time frame.

V. CONCLUSION

The Russian Orthodox Church linked its history with the history of the Russian state. In this situation, the Church could influence political processes. Relations between the state and the Russian Orthodox Church, which developed in the XIX century, did not always meet the requirements of Russia.

It can be argued that, while respecting religion, some authorities accepted political dividends, but did not recognize religion as a fundamental sphere of public life. The state, having subordinated the Church, destroyed the dependence of the spiritual from the secular, which led to the elimination of moral principles in society and internal strife. The clergy recognized the merger of the Russian Orthodox Church and state. The patronage of the Church through secular power prompted religious leaders to the necessity of church reforms. The Russian Orthodox Church collided in the XIX - early XX centuries. with the problems associated with the modernization of the state and society, which manifested itself in the weakening of the role of religion among the masses; in the destruction of the patriarchal way of life; in the development of sectarianism and atheistic sentiments.

At the end of the XIX century, the Orthodox Church was able to create a significant system of religious enlightenment and a missionary capable of preserving the Orthodox traditions of the population in the provinces of the Central Chernozem region. If, at the beginning of the nineteenth century, the spiritual and educational activities in the districts depended on the proximity of a large monastery or on the zeal of the parish clergy, then in the late 19th and early 20th centuries it became the norm for large villages and the city.

The article shows that the Russian Orthodox Church, thanks to its intellectual abilities and social uplift, has become an influential social force, leaving a state of immobility and spiritual isolation from worldly worries. The Orthodox Church in Russia, despite all the difficulties: financial, political, social, managed to determine the main directions of religious education of the population. Undoubtedly, the state was interested in church politics, but secular authorities tried to preserve their own interests in this policy.

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Economic Sciences

THE EVOLUTION OF THE LABOUR MARKET IN SOVIET RUSSIA AND THE USSR IN THE 1920S

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Abstract:

In article focuses on the main milestones in the development of the Soviet labor market, right up to its official closure at the end of 1930, and the first measures of the Soviet government in the sphere of labor hiring are systematized. In this article, the author considers the main stages of the Soviet labour market's evolution until 1930. The first measures of the Soviet policy on the labour market are systemized.

Keywords: History of Labour Market, Soviet Labour Market, Labour Market's Institutions, Combating Unemployment.

I. INTRODUCTION

The labor market is one of the most important economic institutions that are important for the social and economic life of society. Therefore, the study of its characteristics at various stages of historical development makes it possible to imagine what was happening in the economy in different periods.

For the first time in 1915-1916, an attempt was made to organize the distribution of labor in Russia: a large number of local labor bureaus and the All-Russia Labor Bureau were organized, servicing mainly the needs of refugees. Then, the organization of the labor market began in practice only in August 1917; 6 months after the February Revolution of 1917: a law on labor exchanges was introduced. By the October revolution in the country with hundreds of large cities, there were no more than two dozen labor exchanges.

While Russia was at war, there was no noticeable unemployment. The opposite phenomenon was observed: the defense industry and agriculture experienced a shortage of workers, the economic policy of "industrial mobilization" and "labor mobilization" was carried out. There were no free workers on the labor market, so the work of prisoners of war, soldiers and immigrants ("aliens") was used intensively. The use of labor of prisoners of war occurred throughout the territory of Russia during the period from 1915 (140 thousand) to 1918 inclusive (95 thousand). The maximum number of prisoners of war in Russia was in 1917

and exceeded 1.5 million. This free labor was used at various state-owned enterprises: mining plants, ports, timber and peat extraction, on the construction and operation of railroads and highways, as well as in front-line operations.

The situation on the labor market in Soviet Russia has changed dramatically in connection with the conclusion of the Brest Peace. By February-early March, the demobilization of the army and industry actually ended, and the country faced a mass unemployment phenomenon. The All-Russian Congress of Labor Commissars held in May 1918 described the general causes of the depression that had developed in the labor market in April-May:

1. The disorganization of the labor market in Russia has reached its extreme limits due to backwardness, the petty-bourgeois way of economy and the resulting economic dispersion of the country. These conditions strongly influenced the labor market after the war.

2. The liquidation of the war, which had drawn into the sphere of production, as applied to military needs. Millions of urban and rural petty bourgeoisie and created countless institutions and enterprises only for servicing military needs-was bound to create an extremely difficult situation in the labor market by throwing overboard hundreds of thousands of people are alien, by their nature, to production.

3. The return from the front of many millions of soldiers, among whom the vast majority was connected to the land before the war, and a large part - with all kinds of casual occupations, gave the ready army of the unemployed and set the state against this whole mass unsolvable tasks.

4. Along with the vast mass of unemployed who were not fit for productive work to recreate the national economy, a considerable number of skilled workers left the production market as a result of the complete liquidation or partial reduction of work in enterprises serving the needs of war appeared on the labor market.

5. These conditions, which together gave rise to mass unemployment, were reinforced by certain circumstances, namely:

a) the isolation of Russia from a number of territories (the Donets Basin, South Russia, the North Caucasus) because of military occupation, as a result of which hundreds of thousands of workers sent to these regions for mining and agricultural work were forced to remain in their provinces (Tula, Kaluga, Tambov, Voronezh, Kursk, and others);

b) a disruption in transport that prevents workers from leaving for agricultural, construction and other work in remote areas; c) the relations created by the land reform have reduced the field of employment in the countryside.

II. METHODOLOGY

The aim of the study is theoretical analysis and empirical study of the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the labor market in Soviet Russia and the USSR in the 1920s

The subject of the study is the evolution of the soviet labor market.

The theoretical and methodological basis for the study was the statistics and the works of Russian historians and scientists such as I. Khodorovsky, Z.A. Astapovich, O.V. Mramornova, V.S. Rakhmanin and others.

III. RESULTS

Between January 1 and April 1, 1918, prisoners of war (sent home) were removed from work and replaced by unemployed soldiers who returned from the front. Around the same time, the People's Commissariat for Labor passed a resolution on the release of import ("yellow") workers from the operation of contracts, and entrepreneurs were obliged to immediately settle accounts with them and, at the first request of the Chinese workers, take them (at the expense of entrepreneurs) to their homeland, to China. Tens of thousands of Chinese workers left for China. These events have made it possible to ease tensions in the domestic labor market, to free, albeit not better quality, but jobs that generate income.

The general situation in the labor market by April-May 1918 was as follows: within Soviet Russia there were 324,000 (in April), 375,000 (in May) unemployed officially placed on labor exchanges. This number of unemployed was distributed by region as follows:

Table 1.

The Distribution of the Unemployed in Soviet Russia in April-May 1918	
1. The Moscow region	100-120 thousand people.
2. The Petrograd region	50-70 thousand people.
3. The Volga region	50 thousand people.
4. The Don and Caucasus region	50 thousand people.
5. The Ural	18 thousand people.
6. The Black Earth Region	15-20 thousand people.
7. The Transcaucasia	15 thousand people.
8. The Western Siberia	10-20 thousand people.
9. The Turkistan	7 thousand people.
10. The Eastern Siberia	6 thousand people.
11. The Far East	3-4 thousand people.
Total:	324-375 thousand people.

The all-Russian unified network of labor exchanges on June 1, 1918, within the regions controlled by the Soviet government, consisted of 204 labor exchanges, including 73 in the Moscow region, 37 in the Urals, Povolzhskaya - 24, Petrograd - 22, Voronezh - 13 etc.

The economic policy of the Soviet government was from the very beginning directed at liquidating the labor market and creating accounting and planned distribution of all available labor in the country with the help of state bodies for the distribution of labor force-labor exchanges. At first, this was due to military necessity; after the defeat of the white movement - the need for industrialization of the country.

The First All-Russian Congress of Trade Unions, held on January 7-14, 1918, adopted a resolution on "Unemployment". It said: "The struggle against unemployment in conditions of re-organization of society on a socialist basis is possible only through the organization of the national economy, the restoration of the productive forces of the country and the proper distribution of labor." It also set the task of organizing "trade unions of labor exchanges for the accurate registration and distribution of workers and their transfer to those branches of the national economy, where they need"; the necessity of carrying out "a working policy (centralized transfer of labor forces from one district to another)" was justified ".

Thus, already in 1918, the new leadership of the country relied not on the market mechanism for the supply and demand of labor, but on the planned administrative and command mechanism for its distribution in the country's economy.

Proof of this thesis is a whole series of legislative acts of the Soviet government.

First, on January 31, 1918, a new law on labor exchanges was adopted, which abolished private offices for hire and established the mandatory employment of employees and workers only through state labor exchanges. The categorical prohibition of transactions, in addition to the labor exchanges, created a common for all, compulsory labor queue for sending to work. Labor exchanges acted as the only distributors of labor in their way and regulators of all relations that are formed on the Soviet labor market. The factory committees were obliged to hire only through the labor exchange.

In addition, the new law completely excluded from participation in the management of stock exchanges of entrepreneurs. If previously labor exchanges performed the function of labor intermediation between supply and demand and were built on the principle of parity, with equal participation in their management of entrepreneurs and workers, the new "working" labor exchanges were transferred to the exclusive management of workers' organizations.

Thus, for the first time in Russia, a serious disparity was established between the demand and supply of labor. Before the adoption of the law on January 31, 1918 labor exchanges were authoritative for both sides structures - both for hiring and for supply, was observed the important for the labor market principle of parity of the parties - economic forces of supply-demand; after the entry into force of this law, the credibility of entrepreneurs was diminished, which did not correspond to the norms of a market economy.

Secondly, on September 3, 1918, the Council of People's Commissars issued a decree on the discipline of the unemployed (on the prohibition of the unemployed from giving up work), which determines (under special instructions) under which conditions an unemployed person can refuse the job offered to him. Unemployed, according to the decree, had no right to refuse work on the specialty, if the conditions of the work provided did not deviate from the norms established by the tariff of the corresponding trade union. With a shortage of laborers, labor exchanges were given the right to send unemployed workers to other jobs. Unemployed people had no right to refuse temporary work and from moving to other cities or localities. It was established that the work on harvesting bread and delivering food was mandatory for all unemployed. Those who violated this provision were deprived for three months of benefits in kind and money, lost their turn at the labor exchange and were registered as newcomers. Unemployed, who violated the law again, were deprived of the right to be re-registered at the labor exchange, and they were reported to local authorities as persons who do not have certain classes.

The reason for the appearance of this decree was that on September 2, 1918, the country was declared a military camp by decree of the All-Russia Central Executive Committee, and all the economy of the country was subordinated to military needs.

Thirdly, on October 5, 1918, the decree of the Council of People's Commissars introduced labor books for the non-working population ("bourgeois elements") living on unearned income, and for persons who do not have certain classes. Only in the presence of a work record book with a note on the performance of public works and duties assigned by local Soviets, the unemployed received food cards.

Fourthly, on November 1, 1918, the Council of People's Commissars issued a Regulation on Labor Force Distribution Divisions, which abolished the Regulations on Labor Exchange. The matter of accurate accounting and planned distribution of labor in the country was finally concentrated in the hands of the state. To this end, departments for the distribution of labor were established, which were the organs of the People's Commissariat for Labor. They were created in settlements with a population of at least 10 thousand. Labor distribution departments were obliged to take into account all employees, as well as all unemployed in the given area.

Fifthly, on November 3, 1918, the decree of the Council of People's Commissars was published on the introduction of labor service to clear snowdrifts. The broad masses of the peasantry were involved in clearing snow from the railway tracks. Gradually, Soviet Russia went to the introduction of universal labor service in the country and the elimination of the labor market. As a result, a totalitarian, strictly centralized and militarized socio-economic system was created and operated in the country for several years, with the goal of suppressing armed resistance ("military communism").

With the market element struggled in all possible ways. Firstly, the Congress of Labor Commissars and representatives of labor exchanges of the Moscow Region decided: "The congress considers harmful the attempts to create special organizations of the unemployed who oppose themselves to workers' organizations." The unemployed, like all workers, had to enter trade unions; "Could form their sections under these unions and carry out measures to combat unemployment in accordance with the interests of the entire labor movement as a whole".

Thus, in Soviet Russia, there could not be independent organizations of the unemployed, who ceased to exist as soon as in May 1918 the period of construction of the Soviet (state) labor exchanges was completed. The accounting of the unemployed carried out by the exchanges provided "an opportunity for Soviet economic bodies to use the free labor force in the interests of socialist construction".

Mass organs of the use of labor of the unemployed by the organs of Soviet power both in the center and in the localities were public works (the institution of public works was used in Russia and before the revolution - during the First World War to help refugees).

Under the Committee of State Structures of the Supreme Council of National Economy on May 9, 1918, a special state body was created—the Provisional Council for Public Works, which planned these works on a nationwide scale. At the beginning of 1918, the local councils of the national economy, the Soviets of Workers' Deputies, the labor commissariats, labor exchanges, and trade unions were engaged in the organization of public works.

For example, in Petrograd, the question of combating unemployment through the organization of public works was associated with the restoration and organization of production on the giants of the metallurgical industry engaged in the production of equipment for transport (Putilovsky, Obukhov, Izhorsk, Aleksandrovsky plants).

Large-scale public works were carried out in the field of peat development in the Petrograd gubernia, in the Volkhov area; In the spring of 1918, 5,500 unemployed were sent there (for these purposes the government allocated 100 million rubles to the Petrograd Soviet). In large cities: Moscow, Petrograd, Smolensk, Omsk, Rostov and other provincial cities - organized seasonal work related to the opening of brick and cement plants, the repair of public buildings. Work was carried out to improve the urban economy, road construction, the procurement of construction materials for the rural population in need, land reclamation in agriculture, etc. Almost all the unemployed in Khabarovsk were covered by work in public workshops, etc.

On March 21, 1921, the Decree of the Central Executive Committee on the replacement of food and raw materials by natural tax was issued. This was a real event in the political course of the Soviet leadership, which was in connection with well-known events, including in Kronstadt. There was a change in the political and economic course caused by the need to solve the task of restoring the country's agriculture and industry, including by "raising the interest of workers to general production issues" (from the circular of the Central Committee of the RCP (B) of Oct. 30, 1922, "On Industrial Propaganda"). .

"The main stratification factor in the middle and second half of the 1920s was the NEP (which took approximately 5-6 years). The prodnologue opened up new paths for the social and economic evolution of the peasantry (and of the whole society - the Auth.), Including through competition. The convulsion of NEP reduced the NEP men and the bourgeoisie from 8.5% to 4.6%. The main factor in the revival and reduction of the bourgeoisie was politics, but it did not cause either the growth of the working class or its stratification complexity. Its share by 1928 increased only to 12.4% against 10.4% in 1924 ".

An important feature of the new economic policy was the abolition of universal labor service. Since 1921, a course was taken to voluntarily recruit labor for the national economy. The Decree of the Council of Labor and Defense of August 12, 1921 "Basic provisions on measures for the restoration of large-scale industry and raising and developing production" regulated the main changes in the field of production, as well as hiring workers.

First, the largest enterprises in each branch of industry joined in special associations on the basis of economic calculation. Secondly, the procedure for admission and dismissal, as well as the rate of working out and terms of payment for labor, were worked out by the Board of the association (enterprise) in agreement with the trade union and the labor department of the People's Commissariat of Labor. The remuneration of labor should not be lower than the rates fixed by the production union for the corresponding category of workers. This meant that enterprises acquired a certain amount of independence in the search for and selection of personnel; nevertheless, the need for coordination with the relevant authorities remained.

On December 30, 1924, in the circular of the Supreme Economic Council, the People's Commissariat for Labor and the All-Union Central Council of Trade Unions, it was said to all economic and professional organizations that "raising labor productivity is the main and decisive task for the Soviet power." The results did not take long. Already in December 1926, in the report to the Seventh All-Union Congress of Trade Unions, there was a tendency for the growth of industry and the working class. In two years, the output of industry increased in relation to 1923/24. by 130%. The average number of workers in the operating enterprises of large-scale industry was in 1923-24. - 1263 thousand, in 1925-26. - 1901 thousand, i.e. an increase of 50.5% was obtained.

The state of the labor market was characterized in these years as follows: "The movement of unemployment over the past period (1923-26 - Auth.) Shows the stability and even growth of it according to

labor exchanges. Along with the quantitative stabilization of unemployment, there are significant qualitative changes in the composition of the unemployed. For the period from January to October 1, 1925, there was an increase in the number of unskilled unemployed at the expense of industrial groups. Beginning on October 1, 1925, and up to June 1, 1926, the registration of the unemployed at labor exchanges continues to show that the industrial group of unemployed registered with the labor exchange remains unchanged - about 19% of all unemployed, the group of intellectual labor ranged from 20-17%, and the group unemployed who do not have a certain profession and qualifications, from 42-43%".

There was excessive labor, the Soviet labor market was formed; By the summer of 1930, more than 1 million people were registered with labor exchanges. The dynamics of the number of unemployed who were registered with the Soviet labor exchanges is shown in Table 2.

Table 2.

Elimination of Unemployment in the USSR	
1928, April 1	1576 thousand people.
1928, October 1	1365 thousand people.
1929, April 1	1741 thousand people.
1929, October 1	1242 thousand people.
1930, April 1	1081 thousand people.
1930, October 1	240 thousand people.

As can be seen from the table, during each year, from April to October, the number of Soviet unemployed decreased (in 1928 the number of unemployed decreased by 211 thousand people, in 1929 - by 499 thousand people, in 1930 - by 841 thousand. people). This seasonal decline in the number of unemployed is due to their involvement in agricultural work. In April, preparations began for the sowing of cereals, then the sowing, and as the ear spilled and ripened, harvesting took place in the late 1920s manually, without the use of harvesters (they simply did not exist). But by April of the following year the number of unemployed grew again - to a figure exceeding 1 million people. Thus, seasonal agricultural work, which required the attraction of mass manual labor, annually diverted part of the unemployed from April to October, but did not solve the problem of unemployment.

The problem of unemployment in the USSR was resolved by the government's policy of carrying out industrialization of the country, the need to build large power plants, metallurgical plants and industrial facilities that required hundreds of thousands of workers to conduct preparatory, auxiliary and basic works to develop and operate the production. The average number of workers and employees in the national economy of the country in 1913 was 11.4 million. (including workers - 9.8 million people), in 1928 - 11.4 million people. (including workers - 8.7 million people), in 1932 - 24.2 million people. (including 17.8 million workers). Thus, we see an increase in the number of workers and employees more than twofold. Where did this increase come from, quite understandably, from the former unemployed, for whom the Soviet state acted as an employer.

Primary development was given to heavy industry, primarily machine building, which made it possible to bring the country into the category of industrially developed and defensible countries. The needs of the village were pushed into the background. Industrialization required increased grain exports for the purchase of machinery and equipment.

The problem of technical personnel was being solved: the country was experiencing an acute shortage of engineering and technical personnel in industry. In 1928, 13.7 thousand engineers worked in it - 0.5% of the total number of workers. The USSR used foreign technical assistance: representatives of Soviet business executives traveled to Western Europe and the United States, which concluded contracts with large foreign firms. By the end of 1928, 49 contracts had been concluded. Among them was a contract with Henry Ford, who for nine years pledged to provide free technical assistance, transfer his experience and inventions, and the USSR undertook to purchase cars for 300 million rubles from him within four years. Attraction of foreign technical assistance has fully justified itself.

In the implementation of the tasks of industrialization, an important direction was the improvement of technology and production technology. In the oil industry, instead of the obsolete method of oil production, compressors and pumps were introduced, a rotational method of drilling wells was used, and oil refining was electrified. In the coal industry, instead of manually cutting coal, a pneumatic pick hammer was used; In the peat industry, a wide application was made of the hydraulic method of peat extraction. Metallurgy began to master the production of high-quality steel and rolled metal.

In total in 1926-27 years. 528 new enterprises were built. In the first years of industrialization the construction of the Kerch and Krivoy Rog metallurgical plants in the south of Ukraine, Magnitogorsk and Kuznetsk factories in the Urals and Siberia began. In 1927, according to the plan of the GOELRO, construction of 10 new large power stations began, thermal power stations were built in Donbass, Chelyabinsk and Kizelovsk. In March 1927 was laid Dnieproges, which was one of the main buildings of the GOELRO plan. In the years 1926-28. began to build refineries in Baku, Grozny, Batumi, Tuapse; Between Grozny and Tuapse, Baku and Batumi, oil pipelines were laid. Large reconstruction and construction of new mines were carried out in the Donetsk and Kuznetsk coal basins; New wood processing plants, paper mills were being built. Cotton factories were built in Central Asia and Transcaucasia. An important role was played by the construction in 1927-30. Turkestan-Siberian Railway (Turksib), a length of 1500 km., Which connected the rich with bread, forest and coal Siberia with the cotton-growing areas of Central Asia and Kazakhstan.

January 31, 1932 in Magnitogorsk was blown the first blast furnace, six months later the workers put into operation the second blast furnace. This industrial giant was built within two years. The construction of such a giant as the Kuznetsk Metallurgical Combine with a production capacity of 3 million tons of metal per year was also going on at a fast pace. The project for the construction of this plant was developed at the request of the Soviet government by the American firm Freyn. About 1000 days it took the builders to build this first-class giant of metallurgy in the difficult conditions of the severe Siberian climate with insufficient mechanization.

Soviet machine building was developing: in 1933, the first tractors came out of the buildings of the Chelyabinsk Tractor Plant, the Urals and Novo-Kramatorsk Machine-Building Plants (1934) became operational enterprises. The iron and steel industry has mastered the capacity of the factories of the Ural-Kuznetsk Combine and has received new giant plants: Krivoy Rog, Novo-Lipetsk, Novo-Tula. Over the years of the First Five-Year Plan (1928-32), 1,500 new enterprises were put into operation, the second - 4,500 more, and before 1941 - 9,000 enterprises, for the most part heavy industry and power engineering. Absolutely new industries were created for Russia - aviation, automotive, petrochemical. During the industrialization period, coal production increased 5 times, oil - 3 times, electricity - 10 times. The growth rate of heavy industry was 3 times higher than in pre-revolutionary Russia. The number of workers in the pre-war decade increased from 4 to 12 million people. Such an unprecedented pace of industrial development, called the "big leap policy", required huge material and human resources. These resources were received, including through the collectivization of the peasantry and the mobilization of labor of the unemployed.

"Stratification factors after the NEP were industrialization and collectivization, as well as the policy of the final elimination of the "exploiting classes" and unemployment. The factor of industrialization in the 1930s. and acted in Western countries. In the USSR it was industrialization based on state property. The share of the industrial working class in Soviet Russia increased more than 2.5 times (at the expense of the unemployed - Auth.). But its educational and cultural-technical level did not meet the technical and technological needs of industry. The training of engineering and technical intelligentsia was accelerated. The proportion of intellectuals and employees from the late 20's to the late 30's has more than tripled. A new class arose-the collective farm peasantry, as well as agricultural workers".

In September 1930, labor authorities were given the right to recruit unemployed people for compulsory work. In October 1930, it was decided to distribute all unemployed people to work and to stop the payment of unemployment benefits. On November 7, 1930, the Pravda newspaper wrote: "The proletariat of the USSR, in alliance with the working peasantry under the leadership of the CPSU (B.) ... achieved the complete elimination of unemployment in the USSR" and ensuring full employment of the able-bodied population.

However, in reality, the system of social guarantees for workers in the labor market was eliminated. The Soviet labor market in the 1930s. was officially closed. Mass repression, especially after 1934, affected all sectors of society; unprecedented scale took the forced labor of prisoners in the system specially created in 1930 by the General Directorate of Camps (GULAG). Public (paid) work, previously organized for the unemployed, was replaced by state (in fact, unpaid) work in the structure of the GULAG.

In April 1932, the materials of the VCSPS report to the 9th All-Union Congress of Trade Unions "On the Composition of Workers and Employees" stated: "The tremendous growth of the national economy of the USSR is accompanied by the growing involvement of new workers in industry and the socialist sector of agriculture from year to year. Over the entire period since the Eighth Congress (December 1928), the number of workers and employees employed in the national economy increased from 11,552,000 in 1928 to 18,590,500 people by the end of 1931. The absolute growth is 7 million. 038 thousand 500 people or 60.9% "(Table 3).

Table 3.

The Growth in the Number of Workers and Employees in the USSR	
1928	11 млн. 552 тыс. чел.
1929	12 млн. 394 тыс. чел.
1930	14 млн. 360 тыс. чел.
1931	18 млн. 590 тыс. чел.

IV. CONCLUSION

The labor market was a foreign element for the "country of the dictatorship of the proletariat," it could not be fully controlled, since the army of the unemployed represented ballast at the same time and a threat to the newly emerging ("socialist") economic system. Therefore, an economic institution such as the labor market inherent in a market economy and carrying with it certain economic freedoms and problems associated primarily with unemployment of the able-bodied population was unacceptable in the administrative-command economic system.

In this regard, it was adopted a completely logical economic solution for "socialist construction" with a political implication: to eliminate the labor market and turn all former unemployed people into state employees-workers or employees. As a result, the state assumed the function of demand for labor and began to create jobs, that is, it acted as a monopolist-employer for the entire economically active population of the country. The price of labor (the level of wages by industry) was determined from above in accordance with the sectoral wage norms of the State Planning Committee. As for the supply of labor and competition for jobs between job seekers, these classic elements of the market mechanism also lost market power, due to a change in the economic system.

Thus, the basic elements of the mechanism of the Soviet labor market: demand-supply, price and competition-seemingly persisted, but became non-market in nature and economic content, acquired the features of planning and regulation due to total state interference in the sphere of hiring labor. It can be concluded that the Soviet labor market from the very beginning was a quasi-market, which functioned on state orders and served exclusively the sphere of state interests.

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METHODOLOGY OF PRODUCTION PLANNING OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS IN THE CONTEXT OF FOOD SUPPLY OF THE REGION

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Abstract:

Current conditions and problems of foreign policy determine the problem of food provision for the population as the most important. This problem is of paramount strategic importance for the country, since food security is one of the main indicators of the quality of life. Agriculture is faced with the task of determining the volume of production, taking into account the level of monetary incomes, purchasing power, effective demand for agricultural products, raw materials and food, the production potential of agriculture and manufacturing in the region, the dynamics of the price of agricultural products and the availability of spare products.

As a tool for agricultural production planning, it is proposed to use a one-dimensional time series model and construct an additive time series model. As a result, the authors calculated three variants of the forecast of consumption of the main types of food products, which take into account: scientifically based nutrition norms; methodological recommendations for calculating the subsistence level in the regions of the Russian Federation; actual level of consumption. The calculations showed a high degree of reliability of the planned indicators and the availability of an acceptable level of income. The proposed methods allow planning the production, import and consumption of some types of agricultural products.

Keywords: planning, agricultural products, food, time series model, additive model, consumption of agricultural products.

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern conditions of socio-political and economic instability in the regions of the world, the introduction of international sanctions against Russia, from the standpoint of national security, food security for the population as a country in general, and regions acquires special significance. The solution of this task lies with the producers of agricultural products and rural areas. In accordance with the Constitution of the Russian Federation: "A person, his rights and freedoms are the highest value, and the Russian Federation is a social state whose policy is aimed at creating conditions that ensure a decent life and free development of a person". Proceeding from this, the satisfaction of the diverse human needs, the main of which is the satisfaction of the needs for food, is the paramount task of a democratic society. All transformations in society, including politics, economics, culture and the social sphere, are carried out for the sake of man. In this context, the importance of the development of food security both of the country as a whole and of its individual regions is a defining element of the domestic policy of the state.

An important aspect in solving the problem of food provision for the population of the region is the planning of interaction between such processes as production and consumption. The essence of planning the production of agricultural products is to determine the amount of food required for consumers on the basis of scientifically-based norms of consumption. Analysis of the structure of average per capita consumption and its dynamics are the basis for planned calculated indicators in different perspectives. In this regard, there is a need to develop a methodology for planning agricultural production and food consumption, which would allow to accurately identify the emerging patterns and make forecasts of various socio-economic indicators, as well as assess the likelihood of their achievement.

The presented method of planning the production of agricultural products in the context of food provision for the population of the region is the need to present in the foreseeable future the state of food provision for the population, which affects the efficiency of the functioning of the agro-industrial complex and agricultural production as an integral part of it. The difference between the presented methodology is that it uses a complex approach that takes into account the multiplicity of factors. For example, in the partial equilibrium model of supply and demand for a particular type of product, only the reaction of agricultural producers to price changes is taken into account. The calculation is based on the demand of the population of the Kemerovo region for food on the basis of scientifically grounded norms of consumption and can be used in forecasting the management of the socio-economic development of the region.

The main factors affecting the level of food consumption in the region can be summarized as follows: population size, sex and age structure, ratio of urban and rural population.

II. METHODOLOGY

As the object of research in this work is the agriculture of the region. The subject of the study is the planning of production of agricultural products in the context of food provision for the population of the region using models of one-dimensional time series and constructing an additive time series model.

The aim of the study is to model the development of agriculture in the context of food provision for the population of the region.

As methods of research in the work used:

methods of statistical forecasting;

economic and mathematical modeling of development;

methods of the probable state of the object;
methods of regressive and comparative analysis.

To solve the problem of agricultural development in the context of food provision for the population of the region, we apply the method of mathematical modeling.

The agriculture of the region is an example of a large socio-economic system, therefore, when planning production of agricultural products and food provision of the population of the region, there are problems of mutual coordination of interacting in the system participants in this process: producers - processors - food market - consumers. The description of processes in complex systems requires the use of a large amount of data, which necessitates their automated processing. In turn, the effectiveness of the application of automated analysis tools is determined by the balance of mathematical models describing the content processes in a complex system.

When considering the structure of personal consumption of food products among sex and age groups of the population, it is necessary to be guided by the federal legislation of the Russian Federation, in particular Law No. 227-FZ "On the consumer basket in the Russian Federation" of December 3, 2012.

The minimum food basket is differentiated by the main socio-demographic groups of the population: the able-bodied, pensioners, children.

The minimum food basket for calculating the subsistence minimum is developed by the Institute of Nutrition of the Academy of Medical Sciences of Russia. In accordance with their recommendations, the daily energy value of food products should be for: men of working age - not less than 2710.4 kcal; women of working age - 2138.4 kcal; pensioners - 1976.7 kcal; children under 6 years old - 1581.6 kcal; teenagers from 7 -15 years old - 2236.7 kcal.

The final stage of the reproduction process is consumption, which is reduced to the satisfaction of deterministic needs, therefore, there is a close interaction of such concepts as production and consumption, whereas the essence of production is to satisfy consumption needs. The quality of life depends on the level of consumption, its dynamics and composition. A careful assessment of the dynamics and structure of per capita consumption is the basis for forecasting and determining forecast indicators in the operational, short, medium and long term.

In the changed uncertain economic conditions in order to ensure the sustainable functioning of the structures of agricultural production, it is necessary to understand and use the basic principles of strategic management, the implementation of which is impossible in isolation from making effective management decisions. Management decisions should be based on a systems approach, the analysis of those external and internal factors that directly or indirectly affect the activities of the enterprise. With this approach, conceptual and practical significance developments on the problems of making managerial decisions in market conditions will increase dramatically.

In a changing environment, risk and uncertainty, widely used extrapolation methods based on the use of retrospective trends are suitable only for stable economic conditions or within relevant boundaries. There is a need for a strategic approach, the essential basis of which is the definition of the object's mission and goals, the solution of strategic tasks, which products (and above all new ones) to produce, which markets to enter, which business to develop (start, continue, stop).

Modern methods of statistical forecasting allow predicting and revealing the regularities of various indicators, including socio-economic ones, with a sufficiently high accuracy, to carry out reliable forecasts and an assessment of their performance in the long-term period. The forecast provides a scientifically grounded argument for the probable state of an object in the future, possible options for ways and time, when it reaches such a position.

III. RESULTS

To determine the population's need for basic foodstuffs, it is first of all necessary to forecast the population of the Kemerovo region until 2025, and it should be noted that this indicator has been constantly decreasing over the past 14 years. With the help of the mathematical apparatus on the use of the power trend model, the population forecast is calculated.

The tightness of the connection, determined with the aid of the correlation and determination indices, indicates an inverse very strong dependence between the parameters studied (the value of the correlation coefficient "-0.99", that is, the coupling strength, is characterized by the Cheddock scale as very high. The determination coefficient was 98% and the closer the coefficient of determination to unity, the more confident it can be to say that the factor value has a significant effect on the resultant result. That is, the regression equation shows that up to For other factors, it takes 2% of its variance (residual variance [8]) and the regression equation is statistically significant.

The dispersion analysis showed the statistical reliability of the regression equation on the basis of Fisher's F-criterion and the significance of linear correlation coefficients according to Student's t-criterion.

Thus, taking into account the correction of the population forecast, through the use of the power trend model, it is determined that the number of residents of Kuzbass by 2025 will be 2517.4 thousand people, as a result, the population decline to the data of 2017 will be - 9.3%, respectively.

Based on the obtained model data on the population of the region, it is possible to obtain a forecast of average per capita consumption, taking into account the actual level of consumption of foodstuffs and the level of the population's solvency (savings and current incomes).

As initial data for the construction of the forecast, data from the reporting forms of the Department of Agriculture and Processing Industry were used, official statistical data of the federal, regional level.

The most important factors influencing the population's consumption of food products, which are the basis of the forecasting process, are: the level of monetary incomes, the purchasing power of per capita monetary income of the population, effective demand for agricultural products, raw materials and food; production potential of the region's agriculture and processing industry; the dynamics of prices for agricultural products, the availability of substitute products on the market, assortment.

Applying the "Methodological recommendations for providing food to the population of large cities", the following options for forecasting are proposed: the first - taking into account scientifically-based norms of nutrition; the second - methodical recommendations for calculating the subsistence minimum in the subjects of the Russian Federation; the third - is based on taking into account the prevailing level of consumption and the forecast of solvent demand of different population groups.

The authors propose an algorithm for calculating the long-term forecast of food consumption, including: constructing a time series of per capita consumption of each individual food product; the definition of an analytic function that will allow us to describe the dynamics of changes in the time series with the most accurate.

In our opinion, it is with the help of time series that it is possible to describe statistically the development of socio-economic processes taking place in time. The sequence of values of the indicator (feature), arranged in order of increasing time series (chronological order), is called: a time series; dynamic series; a number of speakers. The time indicator, in this study selected individual periods - years.

As the object of forecasting are the processes, phenomena and events, to which the activity of the forecasting subject is directed - the consumption of food products. The subject of forecasting are agricultural and other commodity producers of the main types of food products.

At the initial stage of forecasting, a database of retrospective information was created that contains data on average per capita consumption for each food product of the main type of food - meat, bread and bakery products, milk and dairy products, vegetables and melons, eggs and potatoes.

Analysis of trend series for the period from 2000 to 2015. showed that in the calculation period there was no significant spread of the forecast indicators, the variance did not fluctuate significantly, the unstable economic situation in 2008 and the consequences of the crisis did not significantly affect the actual

indicators. The forecast of average per capita consumption of basic food products until 2025 is proposed to be implemented in accordance with the above algorithm, and using the Microsoft Office Excel 2010 software.

In order to form a more accurate forecast of consumption of staple foods, a regression analysis was performed to assess the extent of the relationship between the variables, based on historical data that is beyond the actual values until 2025.

Using the models of one-dimensional time series and constructing an additive model of a time series, the planned volume of consumption of food products by the population of the region is calculated. In general, the additive model is as follows: $Y = T + S + E$

According to the model, each level of the time series can be represented by the sum of trend (T), seasonal (S), and random component.

The construction of the additive model reduces to calculating the values of T, S, and E for each level of the series.

In constructing the forecast of consumption of the main types of food, the following types of trend lines or regressions were used in the diagrams: linear, logarithmic and polynomial trend lines that are selected based on the form of the dependence of the data on the actual level of consumption of basic food products on the time factor, seasonal and random components.

For reliability of the forecast of different types of trend lines, it is necessary to determine the value of the average approximation error - A, that is, the value reflecting the proximity of the values of the trend line to the actual data. This value can take up to 100%. The value of the average approximation error in the range up to 13% indicates that the average deviation of the calculated data from the actual deviation is not significant.

In the additive model, the seasonal impacts over the period are intertwined, that is, the sum of the values of the difference between the actual levels of the series and between the centralized moving averages and the actual levels of the series.

As a result of constructing an additive model of the time series for meat and meat products, the average error of approximation is in the range from 6.9 to 11.6% and indicates that the average deviation of the calculated data from the actual ones is not significant. As an example, based on the resulting totals, we plot the forecast of the level of consumption of meat and meat products. A similar calculation of the alignment of the input data by the moving average method, the estimation of the additive model of the aligned values of T and the error E in the additive model and on their basis the forecast of consumption for the remaining types of food products by the population of the Kemerovo Region until 2025.

A similar calculation of the leveling of the initial levels by the moving average method, the estimation of the seasonal component in the additive model, the aligned values of T and the error E in the additive model and on their basis the forecast of consumption for the remaining types of food products by the population of the Kemerovo region until 2020.

Analytical alignment for: bread and bakery products is carried out using a fourth-degree polynomial trend; potato - a polynomial trend of the third degree; milk, vegetables and meat - the logarithmic type of the trend line; egg - a linear trend.

When determining the trend component, the following results were obtained:

1) when forecasting the consumption of meat and meat products, the logarithmic equation of the trend is used: $y = 11,297 \ln(x) + 33,389$, the level of consumption by 2020 will be 67.23 kg / year, and by 2025 - 69.75 kg / year;

2) for bakery and pasta - a fourth-order polynomial trend: $y = 0,0125x^4 - 0,3067x^3 + 2,2043x^2 - 4,5977x + 140,21$, as a result, by 2020 the level of average per capita consumption will reach 141,8, and to 2025 - 132.96 kg / year;

3) potato consumption is also described by a polynomial trend, but only of the third order - " $y = -0.05556x^3 + 1.521x^2 - 10.445x + 137.48$ ". It is forecasted to reduce consumption of this type of food: by 2020 to 116.29 kg / year, and by 2025 - 129.44 kg / year / person;

4) Consumption of vegetables and milk by the population of the region is described by logarithmic trend equations: " $y = 11.43 \ln(x) + 46.722$ " and " $y = 8.8032 \ln(x) + 200.81$ ", as a result, actual consumption by

2020 will be 80, 96 kg / year and 227.18 kg / year, respectively, by 2025 - 83.51 kg / year and 229.15 kg / year, respectively;

5) when predicting the consumption of eggs, a linear trend equation was used: $y = 3.2545x + 215.02$, from which the level of consumption by 2020 will be 280.11 kg / year, and by 2025 - 296.38 kg / year.

The reliability criterion of the additive model is the average error of approximation (A), for each type of food product it varies from 0.4% for bakery and pasta products, to 6.3% for meat and meat products, which indicates that the average deviation of the calculated data from the actual is not significant.

The calculated data will be plotted on the graph of the forecast values of consumption of types of products according to the actual level of supply of purchasing power in the additive model for the period up to 2020.

The next step is the application of the mathematical model developed by the authors of the process of changing the per capita consumption of basic food products in time.

This method of least squares, consisting in minimizing the squares of deviations of the theoretical levels of the time series from the actual ones, is used to calculate the parameters of the trend equation.

Proceeding from the chosen forecasting models, three variants of the forecast of consumption of the main types of food products by the population of the region are given, taking into account: scientifically grounded norms of nutrition; methodical recommendations for calculating the subsistence minimum in the regions of the Russian Federation; the current actual level of consumption and the forecast of the effective demand level of different population groups, with the simultaneous calculation of linear and nonlinear trend lines (the selection of the most reliable results by the average error of approximation (A.) The year 2015 is taken for the reference settlement period with which the forecast indicators are compared.

The population forecast and the norms fixed in the minimum set of the consumer basket are taken into account in the calculations of the first variant.

The calculations of the second variant of forecasting the level of food consumption are based on actual consumption and the forecast of the purchasing power of the population, which made it possible to determine the requirements of total volumes in terms of the main types of food. By 2025, to satisfy the population of the region, it is necessary to produce 260 thousand bread and bread products, 601 thousand tons of milk and dairy products (less by 43% to scientifically grounded consumption norms). Consumption of eggs and vegetables and melons in 2025 will exceed the actual level of 2015 by 11 million pieces and 26 thousand tons respectively.

The third variant of forecasting the level of consumption takes into account: scientifically-based norms of consumption, taking into account differentiation of the population by age groups; population of the region. The forecast was carried out taking into account the average actual per capita consumption of food products and its change over a certain period of time.

IV. CONCLUSION

The conducted calculations showed that in order to provide the population with food products in accordance with the recommended standards, it is necessary to achieve by 2025 the volume of production of agricultural products, thousands of tons: bread and bread products - 277; meat and meat products - 198; milk and milk products - 898; potatoes - 264; vegetables - 370; eggs - 687 million pieces.

According to the data of the calculation of the forecast of the demand for basic foodstuffs for the period up to 2025, taking into account the indicators of the average actual per capita consumption of food products, there is a significant convergence of the results of forecasting by different models, which allows us to reasonably judge the plausibility of the forecasts and their permissible errors as of the year 2025.

At the same time, it should be noted that the predicted values reflect only the general trend of variations in the level of consumption for the future and may differ from its actual values. Note that fluctuations in consumption values will be more pronounced, which is associated with the use of exponential smoothing.

Using the proposed methodology, it is possible to forecast the production, import and consumption of certain types of agricultural products. For carrying out forecast calculations it is enough to have data for one year, average annual rates of population change, income of the population, food prices. In addition, the obtained forecast data can be used when adjusting the program of strategic social and economic development of the Kemerovo region for the period until 2025.

In modern conditions for agricultural enterprises (associations), it is important to improve the systems of prospective and current planning - the formation of indicative plans, annual business plans, operational plans of on-farm production units. In the system of long-term planning, it is necessary to intensify the work of commodity producers in developing organizational and economic plans covering all the main issues of rational construction of enterprises (associations), taking into account the impact of internal and external factors, the main of which include: supply and demand for products; territory organization; specialization, concentration and combination of industries; cooperation and integration; mechanization and automation of production; investments; systems of conducting branches of plant growing and cattle breeding. The development of organizational plan is, in essence, the basis for the development of the achievements of scientific and technological progress.

Studies have shown that among the main factors for the sustainable development of the agrarian sector of the economy the most important is the modernization of its material and technical base associated with the development of new efficient technologies in production. The use of statistical modeling methods based on a software package in forecasting allowed the author to develop proposals for optimizing the technical equipment of production.

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Economic Sciences

DEVELOPMENT OF APPLICATION OF THE METHOD OF THE ANALYSIS OF SCENARIOS IN PROFITABLE APPROACH TO ESTIMATION OF COST OF THE OIL COMPANY

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Abstract:

The article proposes a technique for estimating the value of an enterprise on the basis of a profitable approach, supplemented by an analysis of optimistic, pessimistic and basic scenarios for the development of the enterprise.

The results of its application for estimating the value of the oil company are given. To calculate these retrospective data, three cash flow projections for the next five years were analyzed. When calculating the combination of accounting rates of CWM IWACC methods to ensure compliance with the current situation in the company and the market, a measurement of the income and expense scale was required.

Studying the dynamics of stock prices allowed to prove the probability distribution of the implementation of each of the scenarios and to identify the overall assessment.

Keywords: company value, estimated cost, discount rate, cost of capital, analysis of scenarios of sequence of events, cash flow.

I. INTRODUCTION

The basis of business of any company is capital, as it represents the material base of the modern economic system, and is formed and used within certain organizational structures, as well as in a certain business sphere.

Owners of the company have the right to dispose of the entire complex of the enterprise's property. At the same time, the creation of a new business is accompanied by certain costs. The real profitability of the company, compared with the alternative profitability of a similar amount of bank capital, is the amount that makes up the initial basis of the market price, which can be identified as market value. In Russia, the procedure for assessing the value of all types of property is regulated by the Federal Law "On Valuation Activities in the Russian Federation" of July 29, 1998 No. 135-FZ and Federal Valuation Standards approved by the Ministry of Economic Development of the Russian Federation. The Russian regulatory framework determines the market value as follows: "The most probable price at which a given valuation object can be alienated on the open market, when the parties to a transaction act reasonably, having all the necessary information, and the magnitude of the transaction price does not reflect any extraordinary circumstances ... " [1]. In the practice of countries with developed market economies, the concept of value is generally applied without clarifying its link to the market, because it is considered obvious that it is the elements and market participants that determine it. Currently, the peculiarity of the development of market mechanisms is the standardization and globalization of markets, as well as the intensification of competition. Thanks to this, in modern conditions, the concept of "value" is gradually becoming a means of consolidating the resources and efforts of the company to ensure effective management.

This leads to the need to define the definition of "market value" from the position of market capitalization. The above aspects form the basis of the concept of "market capitalization of the company", which implies an equivalent monetary valuation of the entire aggregate of the enterprise's property, financial assets, as well as property and other rights and benefits of the owner from owning, using and disposing of a particular type of business. The benefits of a business owner are financial receipts and various socio-economic preferences (benefits) that are associated with the creation of economic added value in the process of business functioning. Assess the size of the market value of the company is possible in conditions of special evaluation procedures.

Therefore, you can determine the value of the company as an aggregate indicator that is able to adequately reflect its potential ability to satisfy the various interests (financial and economic) of all participants in the relationship both within the company and in its relationship with the surrounding business environment.

You can also determine the market value of the company from the position of the stock market as the total value of the market price of shares of a particular company.

When calculating the company's market value, it is necessary to fully take into account the influence of all the main factors, such as:

- income generated by the target;
- risks accompanying the process of generating income;
- average market yield on analogical objects;
- Distinctive features characteristic of the assessed object (including the composition and structure of assets and liabilities, as well as constituent elements);
- market conditions;
- the current general economic situation and the state of the industry.

The value of the company can also be affected by its relationship with stakeholders. For example, the interests of the owners of the company are very important from the point of view of the formation of its value, therefore, the building of relations with investors becomes more important.

Prospects for the growth of shares of a public company are also important for a potential investor, which can be determined on the basis of analysis, the company is overvalued or undervalued in the stock market. To do this, you need to determine the internal value of the company and compare it with the current price in the market.

II. METHODOLOGY

In the world practice, various methods of valuation of business are used, combined into approaches depending on the indicators underlying the assessment and the tools used.

So, for example, Professor Asvat Damodaran identifies the following approaches:

- estimation of discounted cash flows;
- evaluation by comparing the valuation object with analogs and deducing the dependence of their value on the values of the set of indicators;
- estimation of conditional requirements - options.

In Russia, the Federal Standard for Evaluation No. 1 established three approaches:

- profitable - based on the assessment of expected revenues from the use of the valuation object;
- comparative - uses the prices of analogical objects and a set of comparison parameters;
- Expensive - estimates the costs of creating an object that is similar to the estimated one.

In the revenue stream, the company's value (as well as the value of any company asset) is a function of three variables: the cash flows generated by the company (or its assets); the degree of uncertainty in the forecast for obtaining these flows; time of waiting for the given cash flows (from the investments made).

For a comparative approach, the information base is the indicators of the financial condition and effectiveness of the activity of the valuation object and analogical objects, as well as their prices in the market. The zatrat approach estimates the real current value of the entire property of the enterprise, net of its debts.

Profitable and comparative approaches are recognized in the world and are widely used. But a costly approach characterizes the value of the property and does not take into account either its ability to generate revenue or the investment attractiveness of the market, nor does it require the making of forecasts or the formation of a large body of market information about analogs. Therefore, it is more in demand on the Russian market.

In accordance with FSO № 1 approaches to the assessment of business in the work of VA Shcherbakov are presented. and N. Shcherbakova. However, the collective of authors from the Financial University under the Government of the Russian Federation under the leadership of professors Gryaznova A.G. and Fedotova M.A. complements standard approaches by the method of evaluation based on the concept of economic profit and the optional method of business valuation.

In the work presented, a methodology for estimating the company's value is proposed, based on combining the method of discounting cash flows and scenario analysis. In accordance with this methodology, a study was made of the value of PJSC "AK" Rosneft ".

The valuation of the company is based on a retrospective analysis, since any studies related to long-term analysis require an evaluation of past experience.

It was decided to calculate the cash flow from EBITDA, while the average EBITDA margin for the past 5 years was 21%, the median margin was 20.2%.

As a forecast period, a gap of 5 years was chosen. Three predictions were used to construct the cash flow model: basic, optimistic, and pessimistic. Each forecast is based on such indicators as revenue, cost, EBITDA.

The basic scenario implies the usual course of the company's affairs without sudden fluctuations in financial performance. In the baseline scenario, the revenue growth rate was assumed at 3% throughout the period and the gradual decrease in the rate of growth by 0.3% per year, beginning in 2018. This will ensure an average annual growth rate of revenue of 2.8%. The gross margin was adopted at a rate of 38%, which is approximately the average value in the retrospective period. Similarly, the EBITDA margins were adopted based on the average for the last 5 years.

The optimistic forecast implies stable growth of the company's key performance indicators in the foreseeable future. In this scenario, the growth rate of revenue was adopted at 5%, with a gradual decrease

of 0.3% per year, starting from the second year. Thus, the average annual growth rate of revenue will be 4.2%. Gross margin was adopted at 40% in the first forecast year, which is slightly above the average for the past 5 years. The value of gross margin gradually increases to 41% by the end of the forecast period. The EBITDA margin is adopted at 22%, and gradually increases to 25%.

The pessimistic forecast implies a decrease in the company's key performance indicators in the near future. In constructing a pessimistic forecast, the rate of revenue decline was taken at a rate of -2.0% per year, which gradually increases to a 0.5% increase in the last year. Gross margin gradually declines from 35.0% in 2017 to 34.0% in 2021. The EBITDA margin gradually decreases from 19.2% in 2017, which is 1 percentage point less than the median value for the last 5 years, to 18.2% in 2021. In order to correctly calculate the cash flow, it is necessary to take into account changes in working capital. Given that three predictions were chosen to build the model, a change in equity was calculated for both the retrospective period and the forecast period in the three scenarios. When calculating working capital, the model did not take into account cash and equivalents, since for modeling purposes it is necessary to understand how the business need for these funds will change, whether the company will need to invest money back into its daily operations, or the required working capital will be decrease with sales growth. In addition to operating activities, cash can be spent, for example, on investment or financial activities. This model uses information on the company's operating activities.

To calculate the projected working capital values, the following shares were selected:

- accounts receivable - 8.7% of revenue (average);
- reserves - 4.6% of revenue (average);
- advances given - 6.3% of revenue (average);
- Accounts payable - 15.3% of the cost (average value);
- prepayments - 16.1% of revenue (median value);
- liabilities for taxes - 3.7% (median value).

On the basis of the data obtained, forecasted working capital items and their overall impact on cash flow in three scenarios were calculated.

Thus, in the forecast period, a gradual increase in cash flow occurs, starting from the second forecast year, due to changes in working capital. In the first year, the change in working capital adversely affects the cash flow, which is also related to averaging the shares of individual items in revenue and cost. The total impact on the cash flow is 99.57 billion rubles.

III. RESULTS

On the basis of cash flow for equity, the market value of the company's own funds is determined. The calculation, which is based on the cash flow for the invested capital (total value of equity and long-term debt), makes it possible to determine the total market value of equity and long-term debt of the company.

Thus, the share of borrowed capital of PJSC "NK Rosneft" in 2016 is 66.22%.

It follows that the company actively attracts borrowed capital and the share of borrowed funds is above 30%. Therefore, for cash flow calculations, the cash flow for the entire invested capital (FCFF) was selected.

The usual formula for calculating FCFF is as follows:

However, to build a model, the formula is chosen:

Both formulas give approximately the same result with one exception: formula 2 is more suitable for analysis of retrospective cash flows, since the amounts of taxes for retrospective periods are already known.

At the next stage, in order to bring the value of future cash flows to the current moment, it is necessary to calculate the discount rate.

The economic meaning of the discount rate is the rate of return required by investors for capital invested in comparable objects at the level of risk.

Depending on the chosen cash flow model, such methods are used to determine the discount rate,

such as the cumulative build method, the CAPM model, and the WACC model. Since I chose the cash flow for the entire invested capital (FCFF) to build the model, the discount rate is calculated using the weighted average cost of capital method. Since the dividend policy of the company does not imply the obligation to pay dividends based on the results of each year, it is proposed to use the rate calculated on the capital assets valuation model (CAPM), which is the expected return on equity for investors. The problem of estimating the cost of equity was examined in more detail in.

$(R_m - R_f)$ - the size of the market premium, which is the difference between the expected return on the market portfolio and the risk-free rate; R_c is the value of the country risk premium.

As a risk-free rate, the rate of return on long-term government bonds was chosen, which at the time of the valuation was 8.45%. To determine the size of the market premium and the premium for country risk, data from the table of Professor Asvat Dadomaran was used, which annually recounts market and country premiums for most countries in local currency. The values obtained were 9.24% and 2.56%, respectively.

Calculation of the beta was based on the company's quotes compared with the MICEX index. The beta coefficient was -0.0042, which means almost complete absence of interdependence between changes in the company's quotes and the market as a whole.

The discount rate for the WACC model is calculated by the formula:

W_s - the share of equity in the structure of the capital of the enterprise;

k_d - cost of borrowed capital;

t_c is the corporate income tax rate;

W_d - the share of borrowed capital in the structure of the capital of the enterprise;

k_s is the cost of raising equity (ordinary shares).

To calculate the share of equity in the model, the market value of equity was used, since market and book values of capital can vary significantly.

Thus, the discount rate of cash flows by the weighted average cost of capital model was 6.3%.

One of the elements of the cash flow are capital costs (CapEx).

When calculating depreciation for each year, depreciation of the previous year and depreciation on capital investments of the previous year were taken into account. The amount of tax payments in the forecast period was calculated through EBIT (interest payments were accepted at the level of 2016) by subtracting interest from EBIT and multiplying by effective tax rate, which in 2016 was 36.6%.

In the baseline scenario, the cash flow is smoothly increasing, the value and share of FCFF in the revenue is gradually equalized. Throughout the forecast period, cash flow remains positive.

In a pessimistic scenario, the cash flows of recent years are smaller than the base period flows, which leads to a lower value of the terminal value in further calculations. The share of the cash flow does not have any trend, but its values become more average, the spread is smoothed out.

The cash flow of 2021 is 9.7% of revenue.

One of the components of the final cost in the model is the discounted terminal value (TerminalValue), which is defined as the product of the EBITDA of the post-forecast period by the current EV / EBITDA multiplier. To determine this, you need to calculate the current EV, taking into account market capitalization, net debt and the market value of non-controlling interests.

As of 01.06.2016, the market capitalization of PJSC NK Rosneft amounted to 3,190 billion rubles, net debt as of 01.01.2017 was 1890 billion rubles, and the market value of non-controlling interests was 402 billion rubles. The calculated value of EV amounted to 5,482 billion rubles. The next step was to calculate the terminal multiplier by dividing the resulting EV value by EBITDA for the nearest retrospective period. The multiplier value was 4.8x. At this stage, it is possible to calculate the total costs in the model, representing the sum of the discounted cash flows and the discounted terminal value of the company in the post-forecast period.

Let's take the classical distribution of the probabilities of realization of each of the three scenarios:

- base scenario - 50%;

- optimistic scenario - 25%;

- pessimistic scenario - 25%.

In this case we get the average weighted cost of the company (CV):

$CV = 5924 \cdot 0.5 + 7140 \cdot 0.25 + 4839 \cdot 0.25 = 5956.75$ billion rubles.

Average share price (SV):

$SV = 343 \cdot 0.5 + 457 \cdot 0.25 + 240 \cdot 0.25 = 345.75$ rubles / acc.

During the current year, quotations of shares of PJSC "NK" Rosneft "fluctuated in the range from 294.4 to 425.1 rubles per share. This reflects the moderate market expectations. However, the analysis of the dynamics of stock price dynamics for January-October 2017 revealed the following. If optimistic expectations prevailed at the beginning of the year, then in February-March quotes dropped sharply. During the next six months, quotes failed to break the forecast level of the base scenario and tend to a pessimistic option.

In this regard, we consider it necessary to revise the weight of the scenarios and redistribute them in favor of a pessimistic one:

- base scenario - 50%;
- optimistic scenario - 20%;
- pessimistic scenario - 30%.

As a result, we get the following values of the company's value and its shares:

$CV = 5924 \cdot 0.5 + 7140 \cdot 0.2 + 4839 \cdot 0.3 = 5847.7$ billion rubles.

IV. CONCLUSION

Thus, the analysis allowed to assess the value of the company in three scenarios of its development. The validity of the results is determined by the following conditions:

- forecasting in three scenarios of the company's development of all elements of cash flow based on an analysis of retrospective data for five years;
- use as a starting point in the calculation of the cash flow of EBITDA instead of net profit, which cleared the calculation of the impact of investment and financial components of the activity, focusing on the operating;
- supplementing the model for calculating the discount rate as the average weighted cost of capital by estimating the cost of equity by the capital asset valuation model, which allowed the calculation in the absence of data on the forecast of dividend payments.

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Philosophical Linguistics

LANGUAGE CONSCIOUSNESS AS A SYNTHESIS OF UNIVERSAL AND ETHNICALLY SPECIFIC

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Abstract:

The purpose of the research in this article is to study the problem of linguistic consciousness in linguistics, as well as a description of the universal and ethnically specific features of the formation of linguistic consciousness. The authors describe the principles of studying linguistic consciousness in modern humanitarian science. The article uses linguocultural and linguocognitive methods for revealing the mental and linguistic processes occurring in the linguistic consciousness of a person. The problem of linguistic consciousness and its components is multifaceted and studied by scientists in cognitive linguistics, linguoculturology, psychology, psycholinguistics, intercultural communication. Language consciousness is considered universal and ethnically specific in linguistic consciousness.

The article considers the image that forms the basis of linguistic consciousness and reflects the specifics of the national culture of a certain linguistic cultural community, national perception and awareness of the surrounding reality. Due to the presence of a universal component in linguistic consciousness, communication between representatives of different linguocultural communities is possible.

The national specificity of linguistic consciousness is manifested in the totality of the national characteristics of the native speakers, which include the way of thinking and reflection of reality and the mental warehouse. The study of linguistic consciousness will help to establish effective interpersonal contacts of representatives of different linguocultural communities.

Keywords: Linguistic consciousness, ethnolinguistic consciousness, ethnic culture, universal and ethnically specific, ethno-cultural layer.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the context of the anthropocentric paradigm that studies the features of the representation of language in the mind of a person, especially relevant in cognitive linguistics, linguoculturology, psychology, psycholinguistics, intercultural communication is isolation and research of a category such as "linguistic consciousness", as well as components such as concept, frame, image, and so on.

The modern era is characterized by active interpersonal contacts in the process of intercultural communication. Since the difference in ethnic consciousness can be one of the main reasons for the lack of understanding in intercultural dialogue, for effective intercultural contact, the identification and investigation of a universal and ethnically specific paradigm in linguistic consciousness is of great importance. "It is vitally important to study not only the verbal expression of reality surrounding a person, but also the study of the influence of the language on the consciousness, thinking, culture, strategies and tactics of communicative behavior and the social status of the individual".

The image, which forms the basis of linguistic consciousness, reflects the specificity of the national culture of one or another carrier of the linguistic cultural community, its worldview.

The image is realized in a linguistic sign, which is the result of a person's reflexive mental activity. In the process of cognition, a person creates a world that is both an objective world and a man's own world. A secondary ideal world is created in the human mind, which is a copy of the objective world in the ways and forms inherent in the human brain. The language, which is the secondary form of the existence of thinking, then, as it is expressed, becomes the link between man and the world.

Researcher A.A. Potebnya wrote that "sound is permeated with thought." In his scientific works he writes about the concept of apperception that the perception of the realities of the surrounding world by a concrete person is related to his previous cognitive experience, in which the author means all knowledge, views, interests, emotional attitude. If perception is expressed in a sound reflex, then both perception and image reproduced in memory are perceived by this reflex, and this reflex represents an internal image".

In the mind, there are cognitive processes that connect the inner form with meaning. They form a specific network of relationships, which is the semantics of the language. Values are formed indirectly, relying on the collective experience of people, coded in the corresponding signs of the primary name.

In different languages, the same meaning can be written in the language in different ways. Very often the meaning of a word in any language is considered as a national form of verbalized universal human content. Universal values, which are perceived through their national culture, are painted in a peculiar national-cultural coloring.

In those cases when the semantic, content side of the corresponding words of different languages does not coincide, they are not identical, and the concepts of representatives of these linguocultural communities also differ. Thus, it can be argued that each language creates from its carrier a certain image of the world, which is represented in the language by a semantic network of concepts specific to that language.

The reasons why different nations perceive the surrounding reality differently through the prism of their worldview and perception of the world are differences in the national and cultural traditions, the psychology of nationality, the linguistic personality, the worldview of the bearers of different linguocultural communities. This is due to the presence of many national language pictures of the world on the basis of universal, typological properties of languages as a means of cognition and reflection of the same material world. According to von Humboldt's just statement, different languages are "not at all the same notation for the same thing, but different visions".

II. METHODOLOGY

This study describes the structure and content of linguistic consciousness, a universal and ethnically specific component of it. Under linguistic consciousness is understood the totality of mental mechanisms, thanks to which native speakers generate, understand speech in the process of communication. It is a way of storing language information in the mind; a set of mental knowledge that takes shape in language means - words, word combinations, sentences, texts.

We used linguocultural and linguocognitive methods, revealing the deep mental processes that occur in the language consciousness in the process of verbal communication. The linguocultural method allows us to study the problem of linguistic consciousness in close interaction with the culture of peoples, their carriers, with the purpose of revealing the universal and ethnically specific in the structure and content of linguistic consciousness.

III. DISCUSSION

Actively studied the linguistic consciousness of E.V. Tarasov, T.V. Ushakova, I.N. Gorelov, N.V. Ufimtseva, Karaulov many others.

E.F. Tarasov to linguistic consciousness refers to the "exaggerated" content of consciousness, in which acts of perception are verbalized and information is processed. A more detailed description of the principles of linguistic consciousness is contained in the works of T.V. Ushakova. She identifies the terms "linguistic consciousness" and "speech consciousness". T.V. Ushakova considers linguistic consciousness in a broader sense than a lexicon (a set of nominative units). According to I.N. Gorelov, any content of consciousness can be verbalized. N.V. Ufimtseva developed the principles of analysis, thanks to which it is possible to model the actual state of the linguistic consciousness of the ethnos and, on the basis of these data, restore the previous state of linguistic consciousness.

It should be noted that the linguistic and psycholinguistic studies of verbal associations conducted by Yu.N. Karaulov, Yu.S. Sorokin, E.F. Tarasov, N.V. Ufimtseva, GA Cherkasova, and others. In their works they consider associative-verbal networks. They have identified and described direct and reverse links, which include more than one million words. The data obtained as a result of research by the authors are considered as the linguistic thesaurus of the native speaker, representing his linguistic consciousness. In the linguistic thesaurus, scientists identify the center - the core, which includes a finite number of "knowledge-recipes". The core of linguistic consciousness is preserved throughout the life of man and forms the basis of his linguistic picture of the world.

Until the end of the 20th century, "linguistic consciousness" in Russian linguistics was considered solely as an object of linguistic research. Currently, linguists have left aside the call of F. Saussure to deal exclusively with linguistic phenomena. Attention is drawn to what used to be called extralinguistic factors. Extra-linguistic factors were included in the field of language learning, which should include features of cultural and historical development and cognitive processes. Works appeared Goroshko, Dasheeva, Seliverstova, revealing the national-cultural identity of linguistic consciousness. The collective works of Rostov researchers Sushkova, Kryukov, Siny, on the topic of linguistic consciousness and culture can be noted. The connection of cognitive processes with the process of categorizing a language is considered by N.N. Boldyrev. He analyzes the process of categorization as a leading function of human consciousness.

T.V. Ushakova proposes to distinguish two lines of research on the problem of linguistic consciousness: psychophysiological data on inter-temporal connections and the study of speech ontogeny.

Proponents of the first trend study verbal associations as a result of reflecting the interrelationships that have been developed among respondents throughout their life and form "verbal networks" in their nervous system.

Scientists of the second direction consider speech ontogeny. They believe that the early stage of speech development is informative. Their research is aimed at determining the age and individual norms for the formation of different aspects of the child's speech capabilities.

In the early 90's. XX century in the domestic linguistic science there is an intensification of the research of linguistic consciousness in the aspect of ethnopsycholinguistics (A.N. Leontiev, V.P. Zinchenko, V. Krasnykh, etc.).

IV. RESULTS

The problem of studying linguistic consciousness within the framework of the psycholinguistic approach presupposes studying not only the lexicographic significance of the word. Supporters of this approach are involved in the identification and description of linguistic units that reflect a certain image in the form in which they actually exist in the mind of a person.

For a complete understanding of the category of "linguistic consciousness," let us consider the characteristics inherent in the phenomenon of human consciousness.

Consciousness is the highest form of human thought activity, peculiar only to man. In the mind is a reflection of objective reality. Consciousness is the totality of mental processes that participate in the comprehension of the world around him and his place in him.

In psycholinguistics, the term linguistic consciousness refers to the results of mental activity verbalized by the lexical means of the national language. With a broader interpretation, linguistic consciousness is a mental mechanism that ensures the process of human speech activity.

Man as a biological creature exists according to certain laws, even if it is far from being studied, not always revealed, and sometimes even not at all clear, but the desire to realize one's own nature was, is and will be. A special place in this quest for knowledge is given to language and linguistic consciousness. The study of the lingo-sphere in its various manifestations is being actively continued, the traditional range is expanding, unique units that are singled out in a particular communication act, marginal elements, synesthetic associations are involved in it. The natural ability of human consciousness to associations and analogies suggests that the organization of such activities is realized according to certain, limited in its number models of associative decoding and coding, regularly used by speakers of all languages. The next step is the logical conclusion that they have a universal character and can be classified as typical. A single, undifferentiated view of the world is also needed to try to penetrate the origins of the language, advance the answer to the question of the arbitrariness / involuntary nature of a linguistic sign, develop methodologies and test methods for studying the peculiarities of linguistic consciousness in different languages. make a conclusion about a single way of structuring an attitude assessment to an object regardless of the modality being set, which indirectly proves the existence of uniform semantic the co-ordinate of subjective experience, reveals the mechanisms that ensure its unity.

In the linguistic consciousness, at the level of unconscious mechanisms of right-brain thinking, synesthetic laws are clearly distinguished, which constitute the universal basis of polymodal perception in general and sound-color associativity in particular.

The linguistic consciousness of the speakers of Russian, English, or any language in general is formed taking into account the mass of extra-linguistic factors that make it possible to reach the level of the unconscious from the unconscious, where natural, cultural, confessional, symbolic and many others are recorded signs correcting the national picture of JCA. This part of the system is already more variable, dynamic, but still relatively stable, as it reflects the linguistic consciousness of the nation: symbolism, of course, is ethnically motivated (although there are archetypal features that are universal in essence.). And the third part of the indissoluble unity of human consciousness is a unique personality with associative links and attitudes inherent only in it, which forms an individual component that goes to the level of consciousness and is reflected in any type of speech activity.

To the linguistic consciousness E.F. Tarasov attributes all the "exaggerated" content of consciousness, where the boundaries of linguistic consciousness are determined by the possibility of the verbal results of acts of perception and processing of information. In the opinion of T.V. Ushakovoy, linguistic consciousness is a broader phenomenon than vocabulary, which means a set of nominal units.

The study of linguistic consciousness in the ethnopsycholinguistic direction was theoretically first substantiated in the works of A.N. Leontief. He believed that objective activity is of great importance for the development of consciousness. His teaching was expanded and supplemented by V.P. Zinchenko.

"Consciousness in its immediacy," writes A.N. Leontiev, there is a picture of the world that is revealed to the subject, into which he himself enters, his actions and states. The function of consciousness is that a subject can act on the basis of an emerging subjective image.

In the structure of the individual consciousness, A.N. Leontiev singled out three components of consciousness: the sensory tissue of perception (or image), meaning and meaning.

The main components of consciousness in his teaching are values that transmit knowledge from generation to generation, become an ideal form of existence of the objective world and are constantly reproduced in the consciousness of a particular person. However, in a person's mind, values are not the only components. Since the values, on the one hand, belong to society, and on the other hand, being appropriated by the individual consciousness of a particular person, they acquire a personal meaning, that is, individualized and subjectivized.

According to the scientist, the first component (the sensory tissue of the image) contributes to the formation of a sensory composition of images of reality. In this case A.N. Leont'ev emphasizes as its main function that they give reality a conscious picture of the world. Being the most important basis for the formation of consciousness, the second component (meaning) is "the ideal form of the existence of the objective world, its properties, connections and relations" discovered by cumulative public practice "(Leont'ev 1975: 141). Thus, the surrounding reality is perceived by a person through the prism of values that are formed under the influence of the characteristics of a specific native speaker and his previous experience. The third component (personal meaning) is bias. Many scholars note here that meaning always expresses the relation of the subject to reality, and values are determined by the national culture of the native speakers, that is, they express the "connection of this consciousness with the public consciousness, with culture" [Zinchenko 1991: 23]. According to the approach under consideration, the basis for the formation of linguistic consciousness is the function of activity. According to A.N. Leontief, co "is not a plane, not even an ability filled with images and processes, it is not the connections of its individual" units ", but the internal movement of activity that realizes the real life of a person in society".

Confirming that these three "generators" do not fully provide a link between consciousness and being, V.P. Zinchenko (1988) proposed introducing biodynamic tissue of motion and action. In the proposed scheme, he distinguishes between reflexive (reflective-contemplative) and a layer of being in the structure of consciousness. The meaning and meaning refer to the reflexive layer of consciousness and the biodynamic structure of activity, action and sensory tissue to being.

Later in his works, V.P. Zinchenko introduces the following layers of consciousness - spiritual, and then chronotypic and valuable.

Since a person is a representative of a certain linguistic and cultural community, his life proceeds in a certain culture, many scholars speak of the ethnocentrism of consciousness, which is the result of the interaction of the national language and culture, language. N. Ufimtsev believes that the structure of individual consciousness is a kind of universal. And the content of consciousness, in her opinion, is culturally conditioned and represents a special system of "organizing the elements of experience, which in themselves are not always unique and are repeated in different cultures". I.V. Privalov in his works, on the problems of studying linguistic consciousness, believes that culturally conscious consciousness includes knowledge of cultural objects, as well as rules and norms of communicative behavior. Under the ethnolinguistic consciousness, the author understands the totality of "cognitive-emotional and cost structures, the national marking of which ensures their variability from one culture to another". V.V. Krasnykh writes about the national and cultural conditionality of linguistic consciousness.

Thus, the main components in the formation of the linguistic consciousness of man are culture, nation and ethnos.

"Ethnic Consciousness" R.H. Khairullina - determines the prism of the reflection of the objective world by one or another person in the light of its cultural and historical development. In the light of the above, ethnolinguistic consciousness is a linguistic consciousness of ethnos and national culture.

Ethnolinguistic consciousness is "an ensemble of cognitive-emotional and axiological structures, the national marking of which ensures their variability from one culture to another".

Since all strata of linguistic consciousness have a national-cultural specificity, it seems reasonable to include in the structure of linguistic consciousness one more layer - ethnocultural. This layer of consciousness processes the received information and colors it with "ethnic paint".

When we single out the ethno-cultural layer in the structure of linguistic consciousness, it should be noted that A.A. Leontiev and V.P. Zinchenko describes the structure of consciousness of the human person, and the ethno-cultural component presupposes studying this issue in close connection with the national culture, ethnos and language. The object of analysis is not the individual-personal, but the national collective.

Since the biological and social essence of a person is the same, does not depend on his race and nationality, it is a mechanism for understanding the world and fixing this understanding in the universal code system. Universal universality is the logical structure of thinking and its forms, such as comparison, analysis, synthesis, etc. Unified logical forms of thinking indicate a commonality of the most diverse languages. For example, in each language there is an orator and listener; in each language there are questions and statements; There are modal and emotional assessments of the speaker of what is being discussed.

Due to the presence of a universal component in linguistic consciousness, communication between representatives of different linguocultural communities is possible. The national specificity of linguistic consciousness is manifested in the combination of national characteristics of native speakers, which include a way of thinking and reflection of reality and the mental warehouse.

Indeed, the life of each people occurs in certain cultural and historical conditions. The person around him realizes and perceives through the prism of the world outlook of his ethno-cultural community. According to G. Gachev, the world appears in front of us in the form of many national images.

Thus, the content and structure of linguistic consciousness are formed from universal (universal) and national culturally designated components.

According to A.A. Leontiev, "at the heart of the worldview and perception of each people lies its own system of objective meanings, social stereotypes, cognitive schemes. Therefore, human consciousness is always ethnically conditioned, one can not translate visions of the world by one person simply by "recoding" into the language of another popular culture".

Each language in its own way conceptualizes the world, creates its own language picture of the world. Language reflects all the features of extralinguistic reality that are relevant to the culture bearers who use this language. However, mastering the language, in particular, the meaning of words, the native speaker starts to see the world from the point of view, caused by his native language.

In this sense, words containing linguo-specific concepts simultaneously "reflect" or "shape" the way of thinking of native speakers.

According to the well-known position, the numerous languages of the world are different ways, ways of spiritual mastery of reality, based on the general principles of human thinking. Language, which is a means of formation and expression of thought, is the language of thought, of consciousness. And consciousness is an active process of reflecting the objective world in terms, judgments, theories.

Since language is one of the forms of thinking, the carriers of different languages differ from each other and the forms of their linguistic thinking. Each language has its own ways of conceptualizing the surrounding world, creating its own linguistic picture of the world.

The language contains all the information of extralinguistic reality, corresponding to the bearers of culture. At the same time, in the process of mastering the language, the native speaker develops his worldview and outlook, caused by his native language. In this sense, words containing linguo-specific concepts form the way of thinking of native speakers.

The problem of nonuniqueness of the verbal categorization of reality in different languages is considered by us as a problem of nonuniqueness of "samples of socially significant activities, in which real activity receives a different division" [Ibid.]. Knowledge of the language means mastering the conceptualization of the world reflected in this language. The basis of each specific language is his own picture of the world. The ways of conceptualizing reality, peculiar to a specific language, are partially universal, partly at the national level, so that carriers of different languages can see the world through the prism of their languages.

A way to see the world, according to R.H. Khayrullina is formed as a result of a certain structuring of ideas, knowledge and sensations about the objective world. "The simulated world," she writes, "is reflected in this language as a result of various ways of dividing the objective reality, its basic parameters-spatial-temporal, causal, quantitative, and many others". The main ways of dividing reality by consciousness and language are assignment, conceptualization and categorization.

The initial way of structuring knowledge about the world is nomination. The way people live plays a role in the choice of the basis for nomination. Different peoples have different ways of denoting an object or reality. Nevertheless, they can be understood under the condition of general background knowledge.

The choice of the attribute, which is laid in the basis of the nomination, is carried out in different languages selectively, because it is due to its significance in people's lives.

In the course of a person's cognitive evaluation activity, concepts are formed in his consciousness that represent the most general concepts that reflect the structure of being. The process of conceptualization is the path from sensory perception to abstract thinking. To systematize one's knowledge, a person identifies something in common. The language system, which is a kind of symbolization of the world, reflects the real world in generalized images. These mental images are based on ideas about the realities of the world. These representations do not coincide, differ in different linguocultural communities because of their different characteristics of living. As a result of the activity on cognitive evaluation of a person, the criteria of value are formed.

As a result of the activity. The conceptual basis of language is universal, and the national conception is formed under the influence of culturally conditioned worldview. So, concepts differ from concepts: the concept of "conceived", and the concept of "experienced." The logical basis of the mental image.

The same situation is particularly realized in phraseological units, where not only its description differs, but also its pragmatic, axiological and ethical characteristics. The actual task of modern linguistics is the study of the objectification of concepts based on endangered languages. Minority languages of the Siberian North, existing in the form of colloquial dialects, include the language of kettov. Due to its special genealogical and typological characteristics, it is a unique language that requires fixation, preservation and research.

Images and associations associated with the tradition of receiving guests, organization of holidays are close in content, they form the background of the environment of the concept of "guest, hospitality", but in different languages are expressed in different ways. In each specific case, the traditions of the reception of guests, which occupy an important place in the way of life of people, are consolidated in the phraseological revolution, although the general content of the guests' reception is universal.

In the grammatical structure of any language, there are categories associated with the general categories of thinking-time, quality, space, quantity, etc., but their ways of verbalization are different.

For example, the category of time is differently formulated in languages, depending on its understanding. If in the Russian language the form of the past tense is formed independently of the subject, place of action (I, you, he read, yesterday, read a year ago), in Turkic languages, - participation in the expression expressed by the past tense (Basil. Yashan - yashagen). The form of the future tense is also characterized by the expressiveness in terms of the possibility of the event come).

By categorization is meant a generalization of a phenomenon, object or process to a specific category of experience, a category. The experience of life of different peoples is the same because of the universality of man and can not be due to the peculiarities of their cultural and historical development.

The representative of this or that ethnos perceives any object, any reality of the surrounding world not only in its spatial dimensions and in time, but also in its meaning. These values contain intrasystemic connections of the objective world. With the help of values, a cultural stereotype is transmitted, an invariant image of a certain reality of a certain ethnos. Cultural stereotypes are assimilated in the process of socialization. Because of this, culture can not be abstract-human, it is always concrete-human, that is, ethnic.

An example of ethnically specific in linguistic consciousness can also serve as an internal form of the word. Let's analyze some examples of realities of the flora that contain national and cultural information and are the result of a person's cognitive evaluation. For example, the name of the herb is a thistle. This word is of Russian origin. Etymological analysis shows that it is formed by adding an ancient common Slavic word for features and polls, "anxiety, fright".

V. CONCLUSION

For modern linguistics, the study of the problem of linguistic consciousness as a synthesis of universal and ethnically specific is extremely topical.

Language consciousness is a psycholinguistic and cognitive phenomenon that is actualized in people's activities in the process of communication. It is a product of mental activity, which has an explicit expression in the forms of artifacts alienated from the subject of consciousness. These artifacts are closely interrelated with the national culture of a certain ethnos. To identify the national and cultural specifics of national consciousness of a particular culture, an integrated approach to the study of national consciousness in sociolinguistic and psycholinguistic aspects is needed.

The development of the concept of linguistic consciousness in a specific research plan opens the possibility to enrich our knowledge not only with respect to the phenomena of speech and language, but also in relation to the phenomenon of the psyche-consciousness.

Analysis of literature on the problem of linguistic consciousness has shown that the structure of consciousness consists of five layers: ontological, chronotopic, value, reflexive, spiritual. Since linguistic consciousness is closely interrelated with the culture of a certain linguocultural community, we have identified yet another layer - the ethno-cultural one.

The specificity of world perception and worldview is determined not by differences in the structure of consciousness of representatives of different cultures, but by different mental images that are formed under the influence of geographical, climatic, historical factors that create the mentality of the people. Reconstruction of images of consciousness, containing knowledge and ideas about various fragments of the surrounding reality, reveals the universal and ethnically specific components that reveal the peculiarity of the linguistic consciousness of a particular people.

Images of consciousness are the result of a cognitive-appraisal experience of a person's knowledge of the surrounding reality. The basis of the images of consciousness is the experience of knowing the world of the bearer of a particular linguocultural community. This knowledge and ideas about the objects of the surrounding world are expressed with the help of units of language.

The identification and description of images of consciousness transmits information from the mental world that can not be observed, reflecting the close relationship between the meaning of the linguistic sign and the entire system of human knowledge about the world.

The world reflected through the prism of the mechanism of secondary sensations, imprinted in metaphors, comparisons, symbols, is the main factor that determines the universality and specificity of any particular national language picture of the world. At the same time, an important circumstance is the delineation of the universal human factor and national specifics in various linguistic pictures of the world. Since the genetic mechanism of evaluating bodily sensations is universal, the presence of a universal in the linguistic consciousness of a person forms the basis of the general language content, and therefore there is mutual understanding between peoples, and the presence of an ethnically specific determines the specificity of a set of specific national languages, determines the structural and semantic identity of each of them and the national language picture of the world, in particular.

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Economic Sciences

ECONOMIC SYSTEMS AND ECONOMIC INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract:

In this article, the author considers the main typical economic systems; also the institutions are systemized. The economic institutions are considered as the basis for the economic growth in modern economy. The author identifies the main types of economic systems that are historically developed in the economy, as well as the economic institutions that constitute them, which provide an objective basis for economic growth.

Keywords: institution, institutionalization, function, system.

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern economy is a complex multi-level hierarchy of economic systems, where some systems are elements of others. The notion of "system" (an integer composed of many parts) means an ordered unity of interrelated elements and parts that are arranged in a certain order and have a structure.

Allocate material systems of inorganic nature (physical, chemical, geological systems) and material living systems (biological, ecosystems). A special class of material living systems are social systems: from the simplest social associations to the socioeconomic systems of society, characterized by the stability and integration of elements and the variability of functions.

"Economic system" is defined as an ordered unity of interrelated and homogeneous economic elements arranged in a certain order.

An element is an indecomposable relatively simple unit of complex objects and phenomena. The element performs certain functions in the system and is capable of independent existence. In our view, the main elements of economic systems are economic institutions. For example, the institution of the transaction,

which is a bilateral or multilateral choice by contractors of conduct that aims to fulfill certain obligations; the institution of ownership of economic resources and the results of economic activity, and so on.

The tasks of economic systems are to ensure production, reproduction, exchange and distribution, as well as efficient use of resources within certain organizational forms (households, firms, markets, etc.). In economic systems, the behavior of each participant is motivated by personal and public economic interests on the basis of individual or collective decision-making (for example, the board of directors, the work collective, etc.).

In reality, there are several levels of organization of economic systems, within which economic agents interact. Classification of economic systems by criterion of scale and forms of business cooperation of counterparties has several stable levels of organization, namely:

1. Traditional economic systems - households (households);
2. Corporate economic systems - enterprises and firms;
3. Market economic systems - markets;
4. State-regulated economic systems - national states;
5. Global economic systems - interstate and international economic alliances and alliances.

The economic interactions and links that form these economic systems find practical application in economic institutions and are reproduced thanks to them. Institutions create rules and enforce them, thus managing joint human behavior. The term "institute" is used to refer to the customs and behaviors that are relevant to society, to the same extent as certain formal organizations set up for management, public service.

The meaning of the concept of "economic institution" is associated with the characterization of all sorts of ordering, formalization and standardization of economic relations and relations. Economic Institute (Latin institutum - establishment, institution) - a certain form of organization, regulation, regulation of economic life, activities and behavior of agents; element and an indispensable attribute of the economic system.

Economic institutions act as driving forces that initiate and accompany the development of economic systems. Economic behavior and interaction of individuals is formed on the basis of economic institutions that play a key role in the development and functioning of economic systems. For example, the evolution of the institution of the company contributes to the development of the corporate economic system, market institution - respectively market economy, etc. Therefore, economic institutions are a way of realizing the real culture of modern society - the rules and norms that structure interactions between people within the framework of economic systems.

II. METHODOLOGY

The aim of the study is theoretical analysis and empirical study of the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the economic institutions.

The subject of the study is the evolution of the economic systems and economic institutions.

The theoretical and methodological basis for the study was the scientific works of Russian and foreign scientists such as A.I. Arkhipova, A.N. Nesterenko, A.K. Bolshakova. V.S. Bulanova, N.A. Volgin and A. Alchian, S. Woodward, K. Polanyi, R. Coase, E. Durkheim and others.

Economic institutions are directly related to the process of reproduction and the following functional purpose:

1. Institutions related to production: rent, property, entrepreneurship, corporate structure, factory production, cooperative system, etc.;
2. Institutions related to distribution: wages, interest, rent, other types of income, etc.;
3. Institutions related to the exchange and organization of trade: shops, exchanges, markets, fairs, as well as transactions (contracts), etc.;
4. Institutions related to consumption: households, states, etc.

All the institutions that function in the economy are of two main types: institution-norms and institutions-organizations.

1. The norm-institute is a traditional social institution that existed for a long period of time and became a habit for all or most members of the society (law, custom, norm or system of norms). Institutional norms regulate individual contacts, determine the order and method of mutual group and inter-group behavior, regulate the methods of transfer and exchange of assets. This type of institutions acts as an external economic norm, a special mechanism for organizing and regulating the economic activity of agents and is represented by the institutions of the transaction, wages, entrepreneurship, private property, rent, etc. The economy can not function effectively without a well-functioning payment system, the legal system of norms that define well-known conditions.

Norms are imperative (*jus cogens*) and dispositive (*jus dispositivum*). Individuals do not have the right to change the former under the condition of the effectiveness of this legal and economic system, but are free to manipulate the latter. For example, a rule that protects the rights and interests of a minor through restricting his ability to work for hire is one of imperative institutions. The employer has no right to conclude an employment contract with a minor, which provides for the duration of a working day exceeding the maximum stipulated by law. Otherwise, the transaction is considered null and void in favor of a minor employee.

2. Institution-organization is a well-established public institution, designed to perform a certain type of work, usually long-established and well-established. In the economic environment such institutions are banks, other companies that deal with money, exchanges, enterprises (firms), households, states, etc.

Depending on their purpose, economic institutions perform general, specific and specific (specialized) functions within economic systems.

Common to the institutions are the following functions: reproductive (reproduction of resources) and social (transfer to individuals of established in this environment patterns of behavior and modes of activity). General economic institutions represent the institutions that are characteristic of all economic systems without exception. They are common elements for all types of systems, which act as their active organized participants. The general economic institutions include institution-organization: households, enterprises (firms), the state. They express the progressive process of the development of social reproduction.

The special functions of economic institutions are that they perform regulatory functions. Indeed, institutions regulate economic processes, from the formation of demand-supply to market conditions. Special economic institutions are institutions-norms peculiar to economic systems, where unique conditions exist for their development. For example, competition and monopoly in the market system perform demand-supply regulation functions by influencing the processes of involving, redistributing, disposing of resources.

Institutions perform specific functions and reflect the specific interrelationships inherent in a strictly defined economic system. Specific functions of institutions are the following tasks:

1. Solving the problems of cooperation between economic actors, reducing the uncertainties that accompany the process of interaction;
2. Resource allocation;
3. Formalization of transaction exchange;
4. Overcoming the "opacity" of the economic system - the imperfection of information that economic entities have.

III. RESULTS

The transaction institute is one of the main economic institutions, as a rule, formalized by the contract, because the latter is the preferred legal instrument. However, the transaction is not necessarily formalized in the form of a contract or contract that has legal force, but can be fixed in the form of a business oral agreement - a gentlemen's agreement. Terms of the transaction here are transformed into an informal norm, which people still follow in their behavior, because "the agreement (mutual agreement) is more expensive than money." Transactions are ceremonial-symbolic institutions that are based on more or less lengthy acceptance of conventional (under the contract) norms, their formal and informal securing.

Economic institutions presuppose certain freedom of contractors when parties reach an appropriate agreement, that is, they have a dispositive normative character: they are allowed something, forbidden, or

indicate the obligation to perform or not to perform an action or a system of actions. From here one can draw conclusions about the normality of the modern economy as a whole and the strong influence of the institutional environment in it.

Another type of economic institutions of any economy is the institution of private property, which denotes a certain economic (actual) appropriation relationship, subject to legal registration. This institution is a necessary prerequisite and result of commodity exchange, market economy. The economic justification for the existence of the institution of private property is the fact that it stimulates the investment of capital and clearly regulates the possession and disposal of resources that are always limited. The Institute of Private Property was formed in Russia from the second half of the 18th century. Before that time, the Russian tsar, personifying the state, could arbitrarily withdraw property from his subject. The right of unlimited disposal of the estate, the right of ownership to the bowels of the earth, that is, "full ownership", freed from restrictions "in public interest", was granted by the Chartered Gentry to nobles and cities in 1785 as a special privilege. As a result of the reforms of the 1860's. the right of ownership as a legal institution and private property as an economic institution have ceased to be a privilege, have turned accordingly into a common legal and economic norm.

In general, economic institutions represent traditional forms of economic activity that regulate the economic behavior of subjects and their relationships in production, distribution, exchange and consumption. Economic institutions represent structures characterized by the stability, the integration of elements. Thus, the main elements of the wage institution are the salary, the premium, the percentage of sales, the institution of the firm - the existing and created workplaces, etc. The composition of institutions and the institutional links between them streamline the exchange of assets and characterize economic systems.

Economic institutions in themselves, however, do not work, economic progress does not automatically take place. For this, the actions of people, driven by their own needs and interests, are necessary. In the economy of the third millennium, many new rules have already been created and continue to be created, which are the restrictive framework in which all subjects of the economy are put up (sellers and buyers of goods and services). These rules are the guiding and organizing principle. They are represented by specific economic norms and forms of organizations. These are the economic institutions that regulate the economic life and activity of people in the process of reproduction. The simplest form of economic ties, where everything that is intended for sale, comes true by the manufacturer himself, and everything that is bought, immediately taken away and paid for, went into the depths of centuries. Over time, trade and credit institutions (intermediaries) interfere in the relations between producers and consumers, and the relationship between the seller and the buyer is mediated by the institutions of wholesale and retail trade, and so on.

Economic institutions have no physical meaning, they exist exclusively in activities and through the activities of people. They represent the "raw materials" of social and economic integration necessary for a normal human community - they form "rules of the game", based on pre-rational forms of coordinating individual and collective actions. Indeed, institutions are the most powerful resource ever found at the disposal of an individual and subjected to exploitation. Further economic differentiation creates the need for some integrating forces, without the effect of which differentiation separates the economy. The main significance of institutions is that they are forces that integrate a differentiated economy. Consequently, the process of economic development is an institutional integration and includes the organization of new and reorganization of old institutions.

Economic institutions appear regularly in the process of historical development, since society constantly reproduces institutions as the basis of social life and activity. However, if institutions that are ineffective, that is, impeding the progress of society, are reproduced, this will lead the economic system to stagnation, and subsequently to decay and complete transformation. Over time, economic systems accumulate and undergo various changes, including in the structure of prices, personal preferences of agents, etc. These modifications gradually contribute to the evolution of economic systems and related institutions.

Reproduction and the establishment of new social and economic institutions is a process of institutionalization of the economy, which is accompanied by the legal and organizational consolidation of

new social relations. New institutions bring benefits, thereby increasing the welfare of some part of society interested in the emergence of this institution.

Institutes appear, develop and die. The reason for the appearance of the institute is its effectiveness in terms of rational behavior of agents. The reason for the collapse of the Institute is its inefficiency, violation of the relevant conventions and routines. The unsatisfied economic need of a part of society can bring to life the spontaneous emergence of normatively unregulated types of activities that seek to fill up violations of normative interaction with the socioeconomic environment-the dysfunction of economic institutions. Economic activity of this kind can be expressed in illegal activities: racketeering, etc.

Economic institutions are historically established stable forms of organization of joint economic activity of individuals that have a direct impact on all spheres of public life, modifying its immediate participants. The institutes record mandatory parameters that must be taken into account and observed in everyday life, and are designed to ensure order in the state, solidarity and harmony in the society. The Institute of Public Service for Social Protection of Population assumes the existence of a minimum wage - minimum wage with full coverage of the labor market as an element of the market economic system, etc.

One of the necessary conditions for the emergence of economic institutions is the corresponding social and economic need. In the world of work the institutions of slavery, clientel patronage, colonet (the ancient form of renting), serfdom and farm labor were gradually replaced. The artisanal (home, hand) production of a solitary artisan was replaced by an institute of factory production and hiring an employee.

The first monopolies (cartels, syndicates and trusts) arose at the end of the XIX century. as simple conglomerates of enterprises. The same cartel was not originally an institute. It was a contractual association of firms with the aim of controlling the market for the sale of sugar. Gradually, the actions of "sugar firms", which united in order to control the sugar market, became well-known. They were discussed in the press, they were discussed among themselves by entrepreneurs. It was common knowledge that such an association would prevent competitors from entering the market and receive 20-40% more profit. And there were first cartel agreements and industry syndicates. On the basis of new organizational structures, economic institutions emerged - cartels and syndicates. As a result - the emergence of a new form of organization, which made it possible to improve the efficiency of economic activities. Economic institutions form various economic systems and "rules of the game" within these systems on the basis of social economic ties, interactions and relationships of specific individuals and social groups. For the economy to be effective, it needs a full set of institutions of a different nature. Therefore, the operation of economic institutions must be supplemented by political, legal and social institutions.

So, all institutions function within the framework of society, and economic institutions - within the framework of economic systems. They are a form of social organization and organization, a way of regulating and regulating public life. Their action is manifested in the form of socio-economic norms-restrictions, rules of behavior and patterns of activity of people acting as economic agents. Institutes have objective and subjective aspects (aspects). Thus, the institution of money affects many formal organizations, including banks, state treasuries, exchanges that direct people in their pursuit of wealth and wealth. Only powerful institutions are able to fill up real valuable content with paper money and introduce millions of monetary units into social production and trade.

Economic systems and economic institutions provide the creation of opportunities to meet the needs of members of society, socio-economic integration, the sustainability of public life. On an institutional basis, an informational image of the human community is formed, structuring the behavior of agents in the information economy.

Firms and markets operate in the modern economy as interacting economic institutions. Economic institutions interact, they have a direct relationship to the activities of the individual, determining his behavior throughout virtually the whole of his life. The firm and the market act in this capacity, representing interacting institutions that jointly determine the terms of the counterparty's activities. In a functional aspect, the institutions of the firm and the market coexist together, including in the system of their interaction many factors: industrial, labor, financial, etc.

Firms are institutions-organizations that acquire the factor of production-labor-from families (households) and on this basis organize the production of goods. Acquisition of labor by firms occurs through

the intermediary mechanism of the labor market. This is how the modern economy is organized. But this does not mean that it was always arranged that way or that firms are now the only producers of goods. Historically, the economic activity of mankind began with a subsistence economy, when each family itself extracted all the benefits necessary for life.

Subsequently, people discovered the benefits of specialization and began to exchange among themselves the fruits of specialized work. At the same time, the production of goods was first conducted within the household, and every individual needed to produce a resource for each individual for himself. Over time, the specialization of labor developed and led humanity to a new economic institution - a firm.

The main reason for the emergence of firms is that they have proved to be a more convenient form of organizing the production of goods than subsistence farming or small-scale domestic production. Creation of large and specialized firms can achieve more rational organization of production of goods, that is, spend less on these resources for limited resources, and most importantly - to reduce transaction (organizational and contractual) costs. Thus, firms express the complexity of ownership rights to limited resources, including labor resources, and ensure their effective use within hierarchical systems (firms).

"The firm will expand until the costs of organizing one additional transaction within the firm are equal to the cost of implementing the same transaction through an exchange in the open market or with the costs of organizing it through another firm". The point at which the extension of a firm terminates is determined by the combined effect of several factors: a reduction in the income from the entrepreneurial function, as the costs of organizing additional transactions within the firm, inefficient use of the factors of production increase. As a result, the principle of "diminishing returns from the management resource" comes into play.

The fundamentally significant moment and distinguishing feature of the firm are the employment relationships. The very existence of a firm is due to the fact that it contributes to a better distribution of risk between workers (those who seek to avoid risk) and entrepreneurs (neutral or ready for risk). In exchange for a stable pay, insured against accidental fluctuations, workers agree to obey the entrepreneur's external control. Since the market is an uncertainty and a set of risks, then in connection with the desire of market agents to minimize risks and uncertainties, firms appear. The stronger the uncertainty, the greater the advantages of the firm as an institution compared to the market. The existence of market uncertainty means that people must act at their own risk and risk with a high probability of failure. While the existence of the firm allows you to predict the situation for some medium- or long-term period of time.

From the perspective of saving transactional costs, the choice of the organizational form of the firm is complemented by the market opportunities. Each firm faces a choice: what is better and cheaper for it - to hire highly paid staff on the side or to advance along the career ladder and train its own employees (to take costs on themselves, buying the necessary goods and services on the market, or to be free from them, same goods and services on their own?).

It is precisely the desire to exclude the costs of entering into transactions on the market that can explain the existence of a firm in which the distribution of resources takes place administratively (through orders, and not on the basis of price signals of the market). Within the firm, the costs of conducting searches are reduced, the need for frequent re-contracting disappears, business ties acquire the necessary stability.

The administrative mechanism of the firm is also not free of costs, which increase as the size of the organization increases (loss of controllability, bureaucratization, etc.). Therefore, the boundaries of the firm will take place where the marginal costs associated with the use of the market are comparable to the marginal costs associated with the use of a hierarchical organization.

The essence of the institution of a firm is determined on the basis of the advantages of cooperation, when, jointly using a resource as part of a whole "team," one can achieve better results than by acting alone. However, the production of a single "team" makes it difficult to assess the labor contribution of each participant to the overall result, generating incentives for "shirking". And here there is a need for a "controller", which introduces labor behavior into rigid boundaries.

The firm is initially created by a "network of contracts" and in the course of its activity forms a "network of contracts," including labor contracts. The main problem of the company is the choice of the optimal contract form, which ensures maximum savings on transaction costs. Her decision is reduced to the development of such contracts, which would be best suited to the peculiarities of the maximum number of

transactions. The firm provides more reliable protection of specific resources and allows their owners to adapt faster to unforeseen changes.

If a firm belonging to a certain agent has swallowed a firm owned by another agent, but the latter has remained in charge of its former firm as a hired manager, then there may be a loss of incentives to invest (not necessarily money, but time, forces, etc.) in specific assets. If such losses prove to be significant, then it is economically more profitable for firms to remain independent and their relations being built through the market.

Due to the inevitable incompleteness of contracts, the critical issue for any firm is the question of adapting to unexpected changes. But she will be able to obtain the necessary freedom of maneuver only when her employees are firmly convinced that the firm will not abuse this freedom to their detriment. To convince them of this, the firm can bind itself by certain principles, promising (in explicit or implicit form) to be guided by them in adapting to unforeseen circumstances. For example, do not lay off workers with long service lives when there is a sudden drop in demand.

The set of such principles forms the "organizational culture" of the firm: what distinguishes it from the market. Following the chosen principle, even when it is clearly unprofitable, consolidates its reputation of "reliable" and "fair", which gives tangible long-term benefits. Important is the reputation of the company (goodwill) in terms of the ability to cope with unforeseen circumstances (or not provided for by contracts). Organizational culture and its associated reputation are a valuable resource: these intangible assets can be sold by selling a firm. Thus, the firm represents a network of fixed-term contracts between resource owners that replace the market for products and resources and in which price signals play a relatively small role. The firm operates under conditions of unstable economic environment, uncertainty about future prices, volumes of supplies, quality of goods and raw materials, availability and availability of resources, characteristics of trading partners.

Firms change the demand for labor services, act on the behavior of other employers who employ labor, as well as the employees themselves. The policy of firms in the labor market, which determines the number of labor transactions, is explained by the fact that firms do not have an infinite set of economic resources and therefore are limited in their choice of labor force by the function of optimizing productivity.

Firms acquire labor services in the market, transforming them into products, goods and services, which are subsequently realized. Firms demand demand for labor services in the market and fulfill the function of providing workers with jobs, safety of working conditions, etc. Firms supply vacant jobs to the labor market, determining its size and competition. The more jobs are available, the less tense the labor market, since the abundance of jobs provides great opportunities for employment or job changes. The workplaces of the enterprise and the labor resources employed on them are the associated specific assets of the firm that are created as a result of investment (resource costs). The specificity of such assets suggests that their alternative use is less effective than the use for which they were created.

People, concluding labor transactions with the firm, transfer to it their own labor resources: they allow themselves to be disposed in the internal space and time. For an individual, there is a risk of being a loser because of a lack of reserves, if he suddenly becomes engaged in something new, instead of constantly rotating in a certain established circle - going to work and getting paid. Therefore, employees transfer part of their resources to an entrepreneur (firm) whose duty is to take the risk of using them and creating goods. Firms demand a demand for labor services in the market and thereby ensure the full functioning of the market mechanism. In this regard, the indicator of the total number and species composition of firms in the economy is crucial for characterizing aggregate demand in the labor market.

Firms occupy a key place in ensuring the effective functioning of the labor market, as the source of funds needed to finance socio-economic programs, directly or indirectly, are income received by entrepreneurs. It is firms that are the source of payroll payments.

Before entering the labor market, the firm determines the price of its demand for labor services, sets the wage rates for specific types of work, for which personnel of workers and specialists are hired. But there are significant changes in the labor market with the salary rates set by the firm. The thing is that the demand of an individual firm is very small in comparison with the aggregate supply of services in the labor market. Therefore, the firm's influence on the amount of wages for each of the specific types of labor turns out to be

relative. The average market wage rate is set at the industry level, and not at the firm level. Under the influence of market and non-market factors, the average market wage rate for an individual firm appears as a fixed value established at the industry level, i.e. outside the firm.

In the period of reorganization, firms organize personnel sets directly for themselves, pursuing different goals. First, attract the best qualified candidates for the so-called. the signal policy that the firm conducts in the labor market when hiring employees. Secondly, to prevent the opportunistic behavior of the sellers of labor services, because workers can "deceive" the firm, having managed to sell the services of their labor more expensive elsewhere. Industrial, social and labor relations within the firm are regulated by the mutual economic interests of employees and the employer on the basis of generally accepted norms of wages and working hours.

Modern production can have harmful effects, detrimental to the health of workers. An example of economically significant (ie affecting many people) contractual regulation of negative externalities (external impacts) in the labor market is payment for harmful production. Someone needs to work with poisonous reagents, so the procedure for hiring a harmful shop is regulated by the wage rate, pension, medical guarantees (ie, the balancing procedure), and by law. And if there is no unemployment, when people grab for any work, then it will be necessary to persuade a person to go there to work, for which he will be offered something beyond what is prescribed by law.

The firm is an organized structure of transaction management and, in particular, labor transactions based on workplaces. The firm forms several types of transactions in the market: a labor contract, an employment contract, a civil contract or a contract. The party entering the firm as an employee brings work that is economically advantageous within the institutional framework of the firm. The party that enters into a contract with the firm for agency relations brings work that is economically unprofitable within the firm, but is advisable outside the enterprise. Contracts on the external labor market are unsafe for firms (enterprises), and they often try to refrain from them.

IV. CONCLUSION

Now we can make a series of general theoretical and methodological conclusions.

1. The essence of economic institutions of the firm and the market consists in a special way of organizing and regulating the economic activity of agents within certain limits, limited by time, space and circle of persons. The institutions of the firm and the market are the primary "raw resources" of social and economic integration that are necessary for a normal human community. They form "rules of the game," based on pre-rational forms of harmonizing individual actions. Specificity of these institutions is manifested in the priority focus on the regulation of social and labor relations, transactions of employees with employers; regulation of supply and demand for labor services, storage and processing of information on vacancies, salaries, working conditions.

The main economic property of the institutions of the firm and the market is their high "recombination potential", that is, the ability to quickly restructure the proportions of the labor resources used, which do not violate the conditions of stability and the continuous reproduction of society as a whole.

2. The content of the interaction of economic institutions is the coordination, the unique integration of the actions of firms, on the one hand, markets, on the other, subordinating them to the economic interests of the subjects in order to most effectively implement the labor function. The interaction between the economic institutions of the firm and the market, having a supra-individual character, is changing and improving under the direct impact of the development of the productive forces of society, technological modes of production and production relations.

The economic institutions of the firm and the market provide the functions of adapting the social system, formalizing the labor transactions, solving the problems of cooperation, reducing the uncertainties that accompany interaction between them, minimizing transaction costs, encouraging competition. Economic institutions provide the creation of opportunities to meet the needs of members of society, ensure socio-economic integration, sustainability of public life.

3. The effect of the economic institutions under consideration as mechanisms of "distributive justice" is manifested at the macroeconomic level. They "level out" the social situation, compensating for the "maximizing egoism" of employers and managers, which contributes to the reproduction of the inequality of opportunities for employees engaged for hire. Ensuring the unity of interacting institutions, legitimacy and the presence of a motivational mechanism of interaction, the focus on the effective use of the available labor resources of the national economy are the principles of increasing the welfare of the whole society.

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